

Improving Plasmid DNA Production: Comparative Analysis of *Escherichia coli* GALG20 and MG1655 Strains

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Preface

The work presented in this thesis was performed at the Institute for Bioengineering and Biosciences of Instituto Superior Técnico (Lisbon, Portugal), during the period February – October 2025, under the supervision of Dr. Sofia Duarte and Prof. Ana Azevedo, and within the frame of the DIG4BIO project, an EU-funded Twinning Action (grant number 101159993) under the Horizon Europe programme.

Declaration

I declare that this document is an original work of my own authorship and that it fulfills all the requirements of the Code of Conduct and Good Practices of the Universidade de Lisboa.

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Abstract

Plasmid DNA (pDNA) is essential for vaccine production and gene and cell therapies, driving the demand for scalable, high-yield, and cost-effective manufacturing processes, which remain major bottlenecks due to challenges in reproducibility and Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) compliance. Digital twins have emerged as valuable tools for improving process optimization, but their development relies on high-quality experimental data that accurately captures biological dynamics.

This work aimed to generate reliable experimental data to support the development of a digital twin for pDNA production while assessing the effects of strain engineering and medium composition. Comparative shake-flask experiments were performed using chemically defined media, differing in carbon source and amino acid supplementation. Three *E. coli* strains were tested: DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (constructed by *recA* knockout with λ Red recombination strategy), and GALG20, carrying a *pgi* knockout that redirects carbon flux to the pentose phosphate pathway, enhancing pDNA yield.

Medium composition had the strongest influence on performance. The glycerol-based medium achieved up to a 5-fold increase in pDNA specific yield compared to glucose, while the medium supplemented with amino acids produced the highest supercoiled fractions (>76%). The highest specific and volumetric yields were 11.37 mg/g_{DCW}, by DH5 α , and 11.44 mg/L, by MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*, respectively. GALG20 did not outperform other strains, likely because nutrient limitation redirected carbon flux toward less productive pathways. Overall, these results provide a solid and pioneering experimental framework and biological insights to support future kinetic modeling and the development of the first predictive digital twin for pDNA production in batch mode.

Keywords

Digital twins; Plasmid production; *Escherichia coli*; Strain engineering; Central metabolism; DNA vaccine

Resumo

Os plasmídeos são essenciais para a produção de vacinas e terapias genéticas e celulares, necessitando de processos de fabrico economicamente viáveis, os quais enfrentam grandes desafios, devido a problemas de reprodutibilidade e conformidade com normas estipuladas. Os *digital twins* surgem como ferramentas valiosas para melhorar a otimização de processos, mas o seu desenvolvimento depende de dados experimentais de alta qualidade.

Este trabalho teve como objetivo gerar dados experimentais para o desenvolvimento de um *digital twin* para a produção de plasmídeos, avaliando os efeitos de diferentes estirpes e da composição do meio utilizado. Realizaram-se crescimentos comparativos em *shake flasks* utilizando meios quimicamente definidos, que diferem na fonte de carbono e na suplementação de aminoácidos. Foram testadas três estirpes de *E. coli*: DH5 α , MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ (construída por *knockout* de *recA*, com o sistema de recombinação λ Red) e GALG20, contendo o *knockout* de *pgi*, que redireciona o fluxo de carbono para a via das pentoses fosfato, potenciando a síntese de plasmídeos.

A composição do meio revelou ter o maior impacto. O meio com glicerol proporcionou um rendimento específico cinco vezes maior do que o de glucose, enquanto o meio suplementado com aminoácidos originou as maiores frações *supercoiled* (>76%). Os maiores rendimentos específico e volumétrico obtidos foram, respetivamente, 11,37 mg/g_{DCW} (DH5 α) e 11,44 mg/L (MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$). A estirpe GALG20 não superou as restantes, possivelmente devido à limitação nutricional que redirecionou o metabolismo. Assim, estes resultados fornecem uma base experimental pioneira para o desenvolvimento do primeiro *digital twin* para a produção de plasmídeos em modo *batch*.

Palavras Chave

Digital twins; Produção de plasmídeos; *Escherichia coli*; Engenharia de estirpes; Metabolismo central; Vacina de DNA

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List of Acronyms and Nomenclature

API	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient	LB	Luria–Bertani
ATP	Adenosine Triphosphate	LNP	Lipid Nanoparticles
BGH	bovine growth hormone	MCB	Master Cell Bank
bp	base pair	mRNA	messenger RNA
CMV	cytomegalovirus	NIR	near-infrared
CPPs	Critical Process Parameters	OC	Open Circular
CQAs	Critical Quality Attributes	OD	Optical Density
CQA	Critical Quality Attribute	PAT	Process Analytical Technologies
CRISPR	Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats	PCR	Polymerase Chain Reactions
DCW	Dry Cell Weight	pDNA	Plasmid DNA
DoE	Design of Experiments	PLS	Partial Least Squares
DNA	deoxyribonucleic acid	polyA	polyadenylation
dsDNA	double stranded DNA	PP	Pentose Phosphate
ssDNA	single stranded DNA	ppGpp	guanosine-5-diphosphate-3-diphosphate
ED	Entner-Doudoroff	PSS	Production Supplement Solution
EMA	European Medicines Agency	PTS	phosphotransferase system
FDA	Food and Drug Administration	QbD	Quality by Design
FLP	flippase	RI	Refractive Index
FRT	FLP recognition target	RNA	ribonucleic acid
GalNAc	N-acetylgalactosamine	SSS	Seed Supplement Solution
GFP	Green Fluorescent Protein	SC	supercoiled
gDNA	genomic DNA	SD	Standard Deviation
GMP	Good Manufacturing Practices	siRNA	small interfering RNA
gRNA	guide ribonucleic acid	TCA	Tricarboxylic Acid
HGT	Horizontal Gene Transfer	TES	Trace Element Solution
HIV-1	Human Immunodeficiency Virus type-1	USA	United States of America
HIC	Hydrophobic Interaction Chromatography	WCB	Working Cell Bank
HPLC	High-performance Liquid Chromatography	μ	specific growth rate (h^{-1})
		5'UTR	5' untranslated region

1. Introduction

1.1 Plasmid DNA

In recent years, significant progress has been made in developing safe and effective gene therapies and deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) vaccines for a wide range of diseases [1]. In this context, pDNA has garnered considerable interest due to its promising applications in these therapies. As one DNA vaccine has already been approved for human use and several others, including non-viral gene therapies, progress through clinical trials, the demand for high-quality, pharmaceutical-grade pDNA is expected to increase significantly, underscoring the importance of designing high-yield and cost-effective manufacturing processes [1, 2].

1.1.1 Historical background

To better understand the current significance of plasmids, it is useful to comprehend the historical context of their discovery. The term "plasmid" was introduced in 1952, by J. Lederberg, to describe autonomously replicating genetic elements, first identified in *Shigella* as mediators of Horizontal Gene Transfer (HGT) of antibiotic resistance [3, 4].

In the early 1960s, D. Helinski's labeling and density centrifugation experiments confirmed that plasmids are DNA, distinguishable from genomic DNA (gDNA) by their lower GC content [4]. In 1963, F. Jacob and colleagues introduced the replicon model, defining plasmids as independent units of replication, and electron microscopy studies provided the first evidence of their covalently closed circular structure [4].

The discovery of restriction enzymes in the 1970s enabled the controlled cleavage and ligation of DNA, laying the foundations for recombinant DNA technology. This led to the development of the pBR and pUC plasmid families, essential tools for cloning [5].

The field continued to evolve with the classification of incompatibility groups and the discovery of linear plasmids, culminating in 1990 with the formal conception of the field of "plasmid biology" at the Fallen Leaf Lake Conference [3, 4]. Today, plasmids remain central to recombinant DNA technology, synthetic biology, and gene therapies [3].

1.1.2 Plasmids in Nature

Plasmids are extrachromosomal DNA molecules found in nearly all bacteria, archaea, and some eukaryotes, like fungi and mitochondria [6, 7]. They are nonessential for the growth of normal cells, hence they can be acquired or lost without lethal consequences [6, 8]. Comprising part of the bacterial mobilome, they contribute to genetic diversity, variability and environmental adaptability by carrying genes for metabolism, antibiotic resistance and other beneficial traits [9]. Even though plasmids rely on host

machinery for replication like parasites, they often provide beneficial traits that enhance fitness [7].

1.1.2.1 Plasmid structure, function and classification

Plasmids consist of backbone genes, required for replication, stability, and transfer, and accessory or payload genes, that provide adaptive traits to the host, such as antibiotic resistance or metabolic functions. Their modular organization allows them to evolve through the gain or loss of functional gene clusters, often resulting in mosaic structures [6, 7].

Additionally, plasmids are typically circular and vary widely in size, copy number, host range and replication mechanisms, which influence plasmid stability and productivity [7]. Copy number is determined by the mode of replication control, dependent on host-cell or plasmid-encoded proteins. It is classified as high or low depending on whether it exceeds 20 copies per cell cultured in liquid Luria–Bertani (LB) medium [6].

Plasmids can also be classified by their ability to transfer. Conjugative plasmids encode the transfer machinery, while mobilizable plasmids require a helper plasmid. They can be transferred either vertically to daughter cells or horizontally to unrelated bacteria, through conjugation, transduction, or transformation. The latter is exploited in molecular cloning, where artificial methods are used to introduce pDNA into bacterial cells. In Gram-negative bacteria, it involves treatment with calcium chloride followed by heat shock, while in Gram-positive bacteria it involves electroporation [7, 8, 10, 11].

1.1.3 Plasmid DNA as a biotechnology tool

For the past decades, plasmids have been pivotal in the development of biotechnology, serving as the most ubiquitous molecular tool for DNA manipulation, transfer, and gene expression in both microorganisms and animal cells. Plasmids are also of particular interest for the production of heterologous and recombinant proteins, which can replace or restore proteins in patients [12].

1.1.3.1 Design considerations

After a therapeutic gene has been identified, it is cloned into a plasmid backbone, generating a vector for propagation, and delivery of specific DNA sequences. These vectors are constructed from fragments of naturally occurring plasmids, primarily from *Escherichia coli*, and engineered fragments. They have an almost unrestricted capacity for transgene insertion and can accommodate large segments of gDNA [6].

Plasmid construction is relatively straightforward, but requires the inclusion of specific regulatory elements that influence gene transfer. As in nature, pDNA vectors are generally divided into two functional modules: the expression cassette and the bacterial backbone, as illustrated in Fig.1.1. These regions can be separated by restriction sites for molecular cloning, though modern strategies such as the Gibson Assembly allow fragments to be joined together without restriction enzymes [13, 14]. Plasmid size is an

important design factor, as larger plasmids impose a greater metabolic burden on the host cell, often leading to reduced growth rates and lower pDNA yields [15].

Expression cassette

The expression cassette forms the transcriptional unit responsible for gene expression in bacterial or animal cells. It includes regulatory and coding elements such as a bacterial, eukaryotic, or viral promoter/enhancer sequence and the transgene or reporter gene. For eukaryotic hosts, it may also include the 5' untranslated region (5'UTR), which contains introns to enhance expression, a polyadenylation (polyA) signal to ensure messenger RNA (mRNA) stability and proper termination, and in some designs an immune stimulatory sequence to enhance potency. The choice of promoter and regulatory sequences determines the tissue specificity, expression level and stability of the gene product [13].

Bacterial backbone

The bacterial backbone contains the replicator and a selectable marker. Between the backbone and the expression cassette, a multiple cloning site can be introduced to enable insertion of foreign DNA without interfering with plasmid replication or selection, although it is not mandatory. The sequences that directly flank the polylinker are useful for genetic manipulation, as there are commercially available complementary oligonucleotides for priming these regions in PCR or DNA sequencing [6].

The replicator is a fragment of DNA containing the origin of replication site, where plasmid replication begins, and associated genes or ribonucleic acid (RNA) elements that control plasmid copy number. There are three main mechanisms for replication: theta-type, strand displacement, and rolling circle replication. Plasmids with ColE1- or pMB1-type origins are most commonly used in this context, where plasmids are distributed randomly during cell division [16]. High-copy-number plasmids are preferred for large-scale plasmid DNA production since they allow efficient recovery of large quantities of pDNA [6, 7]. ColE1/pMB1-type plasmid origins rely on RNAlI-mediated primer formation and antisense RNAI regulation, that control replication initiation and copy number, through theta-type replication. However, they rely on random segregation to daughter cells since they lack active partitioning mechanisms, making them prone to forming multimers and deletion mutants [16, 17].

The selectable marker is required to ensure plasmid maintenance during bacterial growth, usually by conferring resistance to antibiotics such as ampicillin, kanamycin, tetracycline, or chloramphenicol. This induces selection pressure, guaranteeing that only transformed cells with the plasmid survive. This is crucial since high-copy-number plasmids often reduce the growth rate of their host cells, therefore plasmid-free cells can easily outgrow them. Additionally, non-antibiotic markers can also be used, such as those conferring phage immunity or recessive markers complementing essential metabolic deficiencies. For vectors designed to replicate in both *E. coli* and another host, they have to carry different replicators along with distinct selectable markers [6, 12, 13, 16].

Assembly of recombinant plasmids is conducted via molecular cloning in bacteria. Large plasmids

Figure 1.1: Simplified representation of a modular plasmid, with the transgene (red), bacterial backbone (orange and blue) and expression cassette (green), retrieved from [13].

are best constructed using site-specific or homologous recombination, while medium and small-sized plasmids, are usually constructed using restriction enzymes with posterior ligation. [16].

1.1.3.2 pVAX1GFP plasmid

The model pDNA vector used in this work was pVAX1GFP (Fig. A.1), derived from pVAX1LacZ, one of the most commonly used backbones for DNA vaccine development [18, 19]. pVAX1-GFP (3697 bp) was used solely as a model plasmid, since Green Fluorescent Protein (GFP) has no therapeutic interest. pVAX1 contains no eukaryotic or bacterial region optimizations, and consequently has relatively low manufacturing yield and expression *in vitro* and *in vivo* [20].

It contains the GFP reporter gene, controlled by the human cytomegalovirus (CMV) immediate-early promoter. This promoter is the most commonly used for DNA vaccines, given that it is highly active in most mammalian cells. It also includes the bovine growth hormone (BGH) polyA sequence, a multiple cloning site and a T7 promoter/priming site. The bacterial region combines a high copy replication origin (pMB1, which is pUC-derived) and a kanamycin resistance marker, the only antibiotic approved by regulatory agencies for pDNA production [19, 20, 21].

1.1.4 Plasmid DNA Therapeutic Applications

Since the 1960s, scientists have speculated that administering DNA sequences to patients could potentially cure genetic disorders. By the 1990s, the successful transfer of genes to humans was reported. The first breakthrough in gene therapy occurred in 1990, with a 4-year-old girl born with a severe combined immunodeficiency caused by a deficiency of the enzyme adenosine deaminase, which is es-

sential for T cell function. Therefore, T-lymphocytes were harvested, transduced *ex vivo* with a retroviral vector containing a healthy adenosine deaminase gene, and reinfused in her bloodstream, resulting in increased enzyme activity. Since then, interest in gene therapy has substantially increased, as it has been regarded as a promising and innovative treatment for various diseases [12, 22].

1.1.4.1 Gene Therapy and DNA vaccination

Gene therapy has been defined by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) as a technique that modifies a person's genes to treat or cure diseases [23]. On the other hand, DNA vaccination stimulates protective immunity against pathogens, malignancies, and autoimmune disorders, by encoding a polypeptide antigen [24]. Both techniques require the identification of the target gene or genes related to a particular disease, which can be inherited or acquired, the fabrication of a therapeutic gene, the design of an appropriate vector, along with its formulation, and finally the introduction of the gene into the patient. The production of the plasmid starts with its design and transformation into a bacterial host. Transformed cells are then propagated within a bioreactor. Following cell recovery and lysis, purification is performed with several established methodologies, prior to its final formulation for delivery [25]. After successful introduction into the eukaryotic cell, the intended gene is expressed and the protein will be produced internally, circumventing issues associated with recombinant proteins, such as complex glycosylation [12].

Success in gene therapy depends on the effectiveness of the gene delivery method, which is, therefore, the most essential and challenging step. The ideal vector should target efficiently the appropriate cells and effectively deliver the therapeutic gene to the intended site inside the cell [23, 26].

Additionally, it should also exhibit a predictable dose-response relationship and maintain a low-risk profile in clinical trials. Hence, for effective therapeutic action, the vector must overcome multiple biological barriers. Extracellularly, it must protect the DNA from endonuclease degradation, resist deactivation by serum components, and selectively target specific cells or tissues. Intracellularly, it must promote cellular uptake, escape endosomes, facilitate nuclear entry and release the genetic material only within the nucleus [23, 26].

Nowadays, the most relevant vectors are viruses, such as adenovirus and retrovirus, and pDNA, which can be used either as an aqueous solution (naked DNA) or encapsulated within a carrier [12, 23]. Non-viral gene therapy protocols often employ pDNA or synthetic derivatives, and these systems have been applied for antisense oligonucleotide therapy, small interfering RNA (siRNA), and Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR)-Cas9 delivery [16, 26].

Due to their ability to deliver genetic material safely and efficiently, these vectors have also been explored in the development of DNA vaccines. According to the FDA, a DNA vaccine is defined as "purified plasmid preparations containing one or more DNA sequences capable of inducing and/or promoting an immune response against a pathogen" [27]. The recipient is expected to generate a symptom-free

immune response to the plasmid-encoded immunogen [12]. These vaccines gained attention in the early 1990s, when it was demonstrated that pDNA delivery into the skin or muscle could induce antibody responses against both viral and non-viral antigens. Even though early vaccines showed limited immunogenicity, they provided a critical proof-of-concept by demonstrating that pDNA-based vaccines could induce immune responses in humans without integrating DNA into host chromosomes. This foundation led to the development of second-generation DNA vaccines, with stronger cellular and humoral immune responses [28, 29].

Both viral and non-viral vectors have been explored as delivery strategies, each offering distinct advantages and limitations depending on the therapeutic objective. As outlined in Fig.1.2A, viral vectors remain the predominant choice for gene delivery due to their high transfection efficiency. However, they also present several challenges. For instance, retroviral vectors present a higher risk of integration of foreign DNA into human chromosomes, which has been linked to severe immune and inflammatory responses in early clinical trials, including patients' death. Additionally, viral vectors can be associated with carcinogenicity, immunogenicity, and broad tropism [26].

A. Vectors used in Gene Therapy Clinical Trials

B. Indications Addressed by Gene Therapy Clinical Trials

Figure 1.2: Distribution of vectors and clinical indications in gene therapy clinical trials. (A) The pie chart shows the proportion of different vector types used. Retrieved from [23]. (B) The chart illustrates the percentage of clinical trials targeting different clinical indications in 2023. Retrieved from [30].

In contrast, pDNA-based non-viral systems offer several advantages. The immune response they induce is generally lower, and their production in bacterial cultures allows for simplified large-scale manufacturing due to the extensive knowledge available regarding well-established bacterial expression systems. The production process is faster and easier to scale-up, and less complex compared to viral vectors, which require animal cell cultivations [12, 26]. Moreover, with pDNA the gene size is not limited to the size of the viral capsid. Non-viral vectors also do not replicate or infect host cells, thus avoiding risks of viral infection or genome integration and exhibiting lower immunogenicity, making them

inherently safer [26, 28].

Nonetheless, pDNA-based vaccines often induce weaker immune responses than viral vectors, reflected by lower antibody titers. Hence, to achieve sufficient immunization, larger doses are required (milligram scale). However, this limitation can be overcome by using adjuvants, such as polycationic adjuvants forming nanoparticles in solution, or calcium- or aluminum-phosphate formulations, or alternative gene delivery methods, namely needle-free jet injection, electroporation or gene gun technology [12, 31, 32]. Non-viral vectors also present lower and variable transfection and transduction efficiencies, as well as restricted biodistribution and poor delivery rates to target cells, resulting in reduced efficacy. These vectors are mainly taken up by the liver, limiting their effectiveness in targeting other tissues and organs [23, 26]. Another major concern remains the short duration of gene expression. Since pDNA is episomal, it does not integrate into the host cell genome nor replicate during cell division, resulting in loss of expression in daughter cells. And even in slowly dividing or terminally differentiated cells, transgene expression can be silenced over time [13].

Lipid Nanoparticles (LNP) and N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) are the most widely used carriers for pDNA delivery, both approved by the FDA. However, the stability of LNP can also be compromised by environmental conditions during storage and transportation, and their components may exhibit cytotoxicity upon repeated administrations, leading to cell damage. Regarding GalNAc conjugates, they rely on the asialoglycoprotein receptor in the liver, so repeated dosing may reduce delivery efficiency over time [26].

Novel types of non-viral vectors have been emerging, including proteolipid vehicles, exosomes, and inorganic nanoparticles, which have demonstrated improved transfection efficiency and better delivery to extrahepatic cells [26]. Despite these advances, other pDNA limitations still need to be addressed, such as larger vector size, and the presence of bacterial sequences (including antibiotic resistance markers and replication origins), which reduce transfection efficiency and trigger immune responses [23].

To overcome these issues, smaller and safer DNA vectors such as minicircles have been developed. Minicircles are produced from parental plasmids, containing only the eukaryotic expression cassette and a short segment of the bacterial backbone, left over after recombination, resulting in a compact, supercoiled (SC) DNA molecule containing almost exclusively the eukaryotic expression cassette. Their reduced size and minimal prokaryotic content enable higher and more sustained transgene expression. Minicircle vectors have already demonstrated strong potential in preclinical studies, including DNA vaccination and cell engineering applications [33].

Considering the remaining challenges in non-viral delivery, the development of more advanced gene editing technologies such as CRISPR-Cas9 has become essential to improve delivery efficiency and long-term gene expression stability. To overcome the delivery challenges associated with CRISPR-Cas9 with pDNA vectors, an efficient cell-free approach to prepare guide ribonucleic acid (gRNA) expression

templates suitable for transfection has recently been developed. This method involves the circularization and purification of a linear double stranded DNA (dsDNA) containing gRNA expression elements into compact, bacterial-backbone-free circular DNA expression vectors within only three hours [13, 34].

1.1.4.2 Plasmid DNA Clinical and Market Overview

After decades of preclinical progress, these strategies have now advanced towards clinical implementation. To date, over 1500 clinical trials for human gene therapy have been conducted in almost 30 countries, involving more than 220 genes. The majority of them have occurred in the United States of America (USA), with almost 30% in Europe. As detailed in Fig.1.2A, pDNA is a crucial vector for gene therapy, with approximately one-quarter of the total, combining naked pDNA and lipofection [12].

Gene therapy is now used to treat both inherited and acquired diseases, with significant breakthroughs in several conditions, as outlined in Fig.1.2B. Notably, it has shown effectiveness in treating cystic fibrosis, acute lymphocytic leukemia, spinal muscular atrophy, sickle cell anemia, hemophilia, Human Immunodeficiency Virus type-1 (HIV-1), and inherited forms of blindness. Several major pharmaceutical companies have been investing in these treatments, such as Novartis, Merck & Co., Pfizer, and Novo Nordisk A/S. These diseases represent some of the greatest healthcare challenges, and the outlined therapies have been transforming their prognosis, offering hope where traditional treatments have been proven inefficient [23, 26].

As for DNA vaccines, the first phase I clinical trial evaluated a vaccine targeting HIV-1, and recent studies extended this approach to other diseases, including influenza, cancer, human papillomavirus, hepatitis, and malaria. Recently, DNA vaccines are under active clinical evaluation for a range of infectious diseases, namely HIV-1, influenza, dengue, and Zika, as well as for several cancer indications [28, 29]. To date, only one DNA vaccine has been approved for human use, ZyCoV-D, authorized for emergency use in August 2021 for COVID-19 prevention. This three-dose vaccine encodes the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein, eliciting an immune response that contributes to protection and viral clearance. The integrated plug-and-play technology allows rapid adaptation to viral mutations. Although several DNA vaccines are in clinical trials, none have been approved for therapeutic use yet [35].

Indeed, in the USA, the pDNA manufacturing market was valued at 670 million \$ in 2024 and is projected to reach 3630 million \$ by 2034 [36]. In fact, the largest share of the pDNA market comes from its use as a raw or starting material in Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP)-compliant production of recombinant viruses, antibodies, and mRNA [37].

Overall, the growing demand for pDNA stems from the expansion of the outlined therapies. Despite challenges in transfection efficiency and durability of expression, advances in vector design and gene editing technologies are driving progress toward safer and scalable pDNA production processes.

1.2 Plasmid DNA Manufacturing

The global demand for pDNA has risen significantly in recent years. Initially, pDNA production was predominantly confined to academic and laboratory settings. Over time, its role in the pharmaceutical industry emerged through the production of therapeutic proteins, and the expression and fermentation processes were established to meet the escalating demand for recombinant proteins [38].

However, the industrial landscape has been shifting, driven by the rapid expansion of cell and gene therapy sectors. With this shift, the demand for pDNA has transformed, both in terms of scale and quality, creating the need for large-scale, high-quality and cost-effective pDNA production for clinical and commercial applications. In contrast to recombinant protein production, where the goal is to maximize protein yield during fermentation via bacterial growth, multicopy plasmid amplification and protein induction, pDNA manufacturing requires optimizing the allocation of cellular resources between biomass formation and pDNA synthesis [1, 38, 39].

To maximize pDNA yields, several factors should be considered. It is important to optimize the medium composition, cultivation strategy, culture conditions (e.g. an increase in temperature leads to higher plasmid segregation stability), and both plasmid and host strain engineering. Regarding the cultivation strategy, the type and source of nutrients, as well as the nature of the carbon source may have a huge impact on pDNA yield [21].

Consequently, scaling-up manufacturing processes, with balancing production capacity while maintaining rigorous GMP production standards and quality specifications, constitutes a non-trivial challenge and represents a major bottleneck for the industry and medicine revolution, delaying regulatory approval [38]. Currently, substantial research is focused on the rational design of bacterial strains and vectors optimized for the production of pharmaceutical-grade pDNA [1].

1.2.1 Overview of production and purification of plasmid DNA

After plasmid design for DNA vaccination or gene therapy, the production process starts with the selection or development of a suitable bacterial host strain, typically adapted from *E. coli*, which should ensure high pDNA productivity, in terms of quantity and quality, and robust fermentation performance, to meet the usual upstream and downstream processing challenges. Specifically, the selected strain must enable the maximization of both volumetric and specific yields, while minimizing deletions and insertion sequences and promoting the predominance of SC pDNA [12, 40].

Prior to large-scale production, a pilot-scale operation is typically conducted within controlled laboratory conditions to elucidate key information regarding process parameters, productivity, and quality specifications. During scale-up, each process step and all raw materials must be evaluated and optimized to maintain reproducible biomass quality, that meets the defined specifications. Parameters to be optimized include inoculum and growth medium compositions, operating variables from the bioreactor

and the cultivation strategy, always aiming to improve pDNA yield [41, 42].

Afterwards, the selected *E. coli* strain is transformed with the target pDNA. The resulting cell culture is characterized to confirm the transformation and subsequently used for glycerol stocks to constitute the Master Cell Bank (MCB) and a Working Cell Bank (WCB), in accordance with GMP guidelines [37]. The produced cell banks are crucial for ensuring reproducible large-scale cultivation of the bacterial biomass and must be thoroughly characterized to verify plasmid identity and stability, confirmed through restriction enzyme analysis or additional methods [41].

Then, the WCB is used to prepare a pre-culture of around 50 mL, which is subsequently used to be inoculated as a seed for a large-scale stainless-steel bioreactor (around 30 L). Cultivation is generally performed at 37°C or at lower temperatures, when necessary, resulting in high cell densities and pDNA concentrations. In contrast to shake flasks, bioreactors allow continuous and automated monitoring and control of critical parameters such as pH, dissolved oxygen, temperature, and substrate feed rate [38]. To ensure process reproducibility and consistency, the cultivation must be successfully reproduced at least three times with identical conditions, as required by GMP regulations. At industrial scale, fed-batch fermentation is commonly employed to achieve and maintain optimal growth and productivity [37, 41].

Downstream processing is followed, for pDNA purification and removal of contaminants such as bacterial gDNA, RNA, non-supercoiled isoforms, endotoxins, proteins, and other residual impurities, until a high purity level is met for human use. The purification strategy depends on the required quality grade of the final product. Following cultivation, the cells are separated from the culture broth via microfiltration, batch or continuous centrifugation. Then, the biomass is tested for several parameters, such as pDNA content, integrity, and homogeneity. Suspended cells are disrupted by alkaline lysis, followed by rapid neutralization, or thermal lysis. The pDNA remains in solution, while gDNA, proteins, and cell fragments precipitate and can be removed through centrifugation, pre-filtration, tangential flow filtration, precipitation, or adsorption, for the intermediate purification stage [37, 41, 42]. Final purification has the objective of removing more persistent impurities, including gDNA and pDNA variants. Chromatography is the most common technique to use for this purpose, including gel filtration, hydrophobic interaction and anion exchange, in fixed-bed mode. However, chromatography poses some limitations due to the nature of the stationary phase, affecting selectivity, capacity and internal diffusion. To overcome this, instead of using bead-based systems can be replaced with chromatographic membranes and monoliths. Finally, the resulting cleared lysate, with the pDNA, is further purified through sterile filtration with 0.22 μm filters. The eluate is then concentrated or precipitated, washed, and reconstituted in an appropriate buffer [37, 41, 42].

Other purification techniques have been explored and have shown improved efficiency, including affinity chromatography with different ligands such as amino acid, thiophilic, phenylboronate ligands, agmatine- and arginine-based resins, and ferrite-based magnetic nanoparticles [42, 43, 44].

Then, the purified pDNA is aliquoted under aseptic conditions into cryovials, labeled, and stored under quarantine at -20°C until quality control testing and product release. The pDNA cryovials are used for drug product formulation, in an appropriate buffer for stability during long-term storage or therapeutic applications. The final aseptic filling process is employed under GMP conditions, with product quality tested by sterility and bioburden verification before release. The process is schematized in Fig. 1.3 [37].

Figure 1.3: Schematic overview of the key steps in industrial pDNA manufacturing, illustrating the process from plasmid construction and bacterial transformation through cell banking, fermentation, purification, bulk formulation, and final fill/finish to obtain the desired product. Retrieved from [42].

While downstream processing has advanced through better understanding of protein–nucleic acid differences, upstream stages, particularly host strain development, there is still potential for improvement and optimization [39].

1.2.2 Host strain for plasmid production

The Gram-negative bacterium *E. coli* is the most common host used for pDNA production. Extensive knowledge has been gained regarding its physiology, medium formulation, cultivation methods, genetic manipulation, and industrial bioprocess applications [12].

E. coli is considered a model organism for pDNA production, given its numerous advantages in high-yield, and economically viable bioprocesses. It exhibits fast growth rates, with high-cell densities and minimal nutritional requirements, therefore resulting in reduced manufacturing costs. Moreover, its genome has been fully characterized and there is a wide availability of cloning vectors and genetic tools, which facilitate *E. coli* strain genetic manipulation for high pDNA yield [15]. *E. coli* has also been considered a biologically safe vehicle for gene cloning and expression vectors in national and international guidelines [45].

However, certain limitations are present, such as endotoxin production in its outer membrane and genetic instability, posing safety and quality concerns. Alternative microorganisms, such as the Gram-positive *Lactococcus lactis*, have been explored to address these issues. Nevertheless, when considering the balance between advantages and drawbacks, *E. coli* remains the most appropriate and extensively adopted host for large-scale industrial pDNA production [39].

Among the commercially available strains, the most popular is DH5 α , with a widespread use in several protocols for pDNA replication, delivering reproducible and stable results [21]. Thus, it is commonly used as a benchmark for comparison with other commercial or engineered strains under study [40].

Other strains are also common, such as JM101, BL21, JM109, W3110 and DH10B, with highly mutated genomes [12, 42, 46, 47].

Although the genetic background of both commercial or engineered strains varies, mutations in the *recA* and *endA* genes are almost ubiquitous, to minimize recombination and degradation, respectively [42]. Recombinase A is involved in DNA repair and SOS response, and in homologous recombination via the recBCD pathway, producing a DNA strand exchange. Homologous recombination can lead to formation of plasmid multimers, as previously mentioned. Inactivating *recA* has been demonstrated to have positive effects, in strains such as MG1655, BL21, and W3110-derived strains. It has been reported to minimize the amount of multimers and topoisomers, resulting in a more homogeneous product due to increased plasmid segregational stability [47]. On the other hand, *endA* gene encodes endonuclease I, a nonsequence-specific endonuclease, that cleaves foreign dsDNA, as pDNA, upon cell lysis. With a knockout in this gene, pDNA is less prone to hydrolysis, improving its structural integrity [12, 48]. Another common mutation, present in DH5 α , is *gyrA96*, for the subunit A of DNA gyrase, a topoisomerase II, which provides resistance to the gyrase inhibitor nalidixic acid. The DNA gyrase is responsible for introducing negative supercoiling, thus with this mutation, the enzyme is no longer inhibited, increasing SC pDNA production [12].

Another common knockout present in commercial strains, such as BL21, is in the *dcm* gene, which encodes DNA-cytosine methyltransferase, responsible for methylating cytosine residues in DNA. This methylation enables *E. coli* to distinguish its own DNA from foreign DNA, protecting it from degradation. Additionally, promoter regions exhibit higher affinity for methylated DNA sequences. Although the final plasmid product differs, plasmids produced in *dcm*-deficient cells have demonstrated higher transgene expression levels in human cell lines, making them more suitable for gene therapy applications. However, they were also found to be less immunogenic, thus they would not be ideal for vaccine applications [39].

As previously mentioned, the engineered *E. coli* strains typically commercialized were developed for expression of recombinant proteins or for cloning [46]. These strains are highly mutated and tend to be unstable, with a high mutation rate that might lead to changes in both gDNA and pDNA. For instance, the strain DH10 β demonstrated a 13.5-fold higher mutation rate than its wild-type MG1655 [12]. Therefore, such strains might not be suitable for pDNA production for clinical applications. A more suitable approach is to start with a wild-type strain, usually derived from K-12 strain, and introduce targeted genetic modifications that are expected to have an advantageous impact on cell growth kinetics and pDNA yield [39, 46].

There are several strategies to genetically modify *E. coli* strains. For gene overexpression, for instance, one common approach is the transformation of cells with a plasmid carrying the gene of interest under the control of a T7 promoter fused to a lac operator, allowing IPTG-inducible expression of the target gene [49]. As for gene knockout, a widely used technique is the λ Red recombination system,

following the protocol described by Datsenko *et al.* (2000) [50].

Since most studies on pDNA production focus on only a few strains, there is still room for significant improvement using this approach.

1.2.3 Effect of plasmid DNA production on *E. coli* metabolism

One of the main targets in strain engineering is the modification of cellular metabolism or physiology, as the introduction of pDNA into *E. coli* has been shown to impose metabolic burden [12].

In the past, the term “metabolic burden” was associated exclusively with recombinant protein production, but recent evidence indicates that plasmid maintenance and replication *per se* can also induce metabolic stress. This term is defined as the allocation of resources for host cell metabolism, namely energy and substrates, to pDNA maintenance and replication [15]. As a result, the cellular response involves activating alternative pathways to generate energy, which will lead to cell growth alterations. It might also elicit stress responses, resulting in lower pDNA yields, through decreased plasmid copy number and higher plasmid instability [15].

pDNA synthesis disturbs gene regulation and carbon flux, leading to reduced specific growth rates, retarded growth, lower biomass yields, and increased acetate production [12, 15, 39]. The degree of decrease depends on pDNA copy number, type and size. The reduced growth in plasmid-bearing cells (P⁺ cells) compared with plasmid-free cells (P⁻ cells) likely results from competition for nutrients, energy and cellular machinery between cellular growth and plasmid replication, but the exact mechanism remains unclear. While growth is arrested, protein deterioration and misfolding and difficult carbon and nitrogen assimilation might occur, in response to stress mechanisms. Moreover, due to the mentioned detrimental burden of pDNA synthesis, cells that lose plasmids grow faster and over time P⁻ cells can outcompete P⁺ cells, decreasing overall productivity. To address this issue, plasmids with antibiotic resistance as a selection marker are usually used, although the production of this resistance further contributes to the metabolic burden [15, 51].

At a cellular level, this might induce cell filamentation, reduce cell viability and alter the cell cycle. Cell filamentation is characterized by the inability of cells to divide despite elongation and DNA replication, decreasing growth rate [15]. In fact, it was reported that some genes coding for proteins responsible for cell wall synthesis and septal division are commonly downregulated in P⁺ cells. It may also be a consequence of triggering the SOS stress response, causing plasmid segregational instability [51].

1.2.3.1 Metabolic alterations of plasmid maintenance and replication

Resorting to high-throughput analytical tools, including DNA microarrays, quantitative real-time PCR and metabolite flux analysis, researchers have acquired vast transcriptome, proteome, metabolome and fluxome data, enabling them to gain deeper knowledge on metabolic burden. These tools allow for the simulation of metabolic behavior under different conditions and identify possible targets for improvement

[15, 39]. Some studies have highlighted some alterations on the central metabolism of *E. coli*, namely in glycolysis, TCA cycle and the PP pathway [39].

The main catabolic route of carbohydrates is the glycolytic pathway, to provide energy and produce precursors for biosynthesis. It encompasses ten reactions, involving different enzymes. Carbohydrates start the cycle, and glucose is broken down into pyruvate, which, in turn, is converted into acetyl-CoA, that will feed into the TCA cycle. This cycle is essential for the complete oxidation of acetyl-CoA, which completes glycolysis. Several TCA intermediates are used during pyrimidine, heme and amino acid biosynthesis, including oxaloacetate (OAA) and α -ketoglutarate (AKG) in the latter [39, 51].

The PP pathway is the second main route for glucose metabolism, following glycolysis. It has the role of breaking down sugars that can't be fed to other pathways, as ribose or xilose, producing reducing power for biosynthesis, and is also involved in the biosynthesis of nucleic acids, amino acids, vitamins and lipopolysaccharides. Most genes are constitutively expressed and not regulated by transcriptional factors, in contrast to glycolytic genes. During this pathway, some precursors for nucleotide and aromatic amino acid biosynthesis are synthesized, namely ribose-5-phosphate and erythrose-4-phosphate, during the non-oxidative phase. In the oxidative phase, NADPH is synthesized by glucose 6-phosphate-1-dehydrogenase (Zwf) and 6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase, essential for biosynthetic reactions. An increased availability of NADPH has been shown to improve pDNA production, since it increases the reducing power both for pDNA and antibiotic resistance synthesis [39, 52]. Alternative routes for glucose catabolism are also present, such as the ED pathway, although they play a less predominant role [18].

In some studies, in most P⁺ cells, most glycolytic genes were observed to be downregulated, while in others those genes were upregulated, specifically with the pyruvate kinase gene (*pykF*), indicating that this could depend on different fermentation strategies [15, 39, 51]. However, two isoenzyme genes of phosphofructokinase and one isoenzyme gene of pyruvate kinase, which catalyze the irreversible steps of glycolysis, were significantly downregulated. These observations probably translate in a reduction in energy production and biosynthetic capacity in P⁺ cells. In contrast, in these cells more TCA cycle genes were upregulated, while being downregulated in enzymes involved in the glyoxylate shunt activity. The latter is a bypass pathway of the TCA cycle to conserve carbon for biosynthesis, if cells are growing on acetate, fatty acids or ethanol [15, 51].

Regarding the PP pathway, in some studies it was noted that the expression of its enzyme genes remained constant even with changes in glycolytic flux due to different carbon sources, suggesting that these genes are expressed steadily. However, other studies have reported a downregulation in both PP pathway and gluconeogenesis [15, 51].

Concerning energy metabolism, it has been observed that the expression levels of Adenosine Triphosphate (ATP) synthesis can either increase or decrease under different conditions, suggesting it might be influenced by the fermentation strategy employed. It was also observed alterations in protein levels,

related to ribosomal proteins and amino acid and protein synthesis [15].

Surprisingly, some genes involved on purine and pyrimidine synthesis are downregulated in P⁺ cells, while the expression levels of heat-shock proteins and genes are higher, corroborating the possible activation of stress mechanisms. Also, it was reported that P⁺ cells had higher expression of acetate synthesis genes, such as *ackA*, increasing its production, which negatively affects pDNA production [15].

Although not entirely coherent, it is suggested that P⁺ cells may resort to alternative respiratory pathways for energy production, with most biosynthetic pathways, including those for pDNA replication, being downregulated [15].

1.2.3.2 Rational strain design to overcome metabolic burden

Metabolic studies on P⁺ cells have provided valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms, enabling the identification of potential genetic engineering targets to enhance pDNA production through gene knockouts or overexpression strategies [15, 39].

The desirable phenotypes that researchers aim to achieve with engineering *E. coli* strains include having the ability to achieve high cell density and high plasmid copy number, minimize the generation of P⁻ cells, reduce possible plasmid recombination, and be compatible with purification procedures [53].

In addition to the genes previously mentioned that improve pDNA quality (*endA*, *recA*, *gyrA96*), another promising approach to alleviate the metabolic burden and achieve the desired phenotypes involves modifying genes of the central carbon metabolism to redirect flux toward the synthesis of nucleotide and amino acid precursors, while reducing the accumulation of acetate [39, 53].

A common issue during *E. coli* fermentation is the accumulation of acetate as a byproduct, which occurs when the carbon uptake rate exceeds a critical threshold, even under fully aerobic conditions. This phenomenon, known as overflow metabolism, results from an imbalance between carbon fluxes in glycolysis and the TCA cycle. Under nutrient-rich conditions, acetyl-CoA is generated more rapidly than the TCA cycle can process it. To regenerate cofactors and recycle coenzymes, cells convert excess pyruvate or acetyl-CoA into acetate. Acetate accumulates in the medium, since it is only consumed once other carbon sources, namely glucose and glycerol, have been consumed. The accumulation of acetate negatively affects *E. coli* physiology and reduces pDNA content. At high concentrations, acetate inhibits cell growth by lowering the extracellular pH. Its protonated form can freely diffuse across the cell membrane and dissociate within the cytoplasm, increasing osmotic pressure and forcing the cell to decrease other anionic pools to maintain homeostasis. Acetate production also is undesirable since it shuttles carbon away from nucleotide synthesis [12, 39, 40, 54].

In P⁺ cells, the carbon flux normally directed to the PP pathway may be insufficient to meet the metabolic demands that result from pDNA maintenance and replication, also contributing to overflow metabolism. Thus, redirecting additional flux from glycolysis toward the PP pathway represents a promising strategy to mitigate overflow metabolism, alleviating metabolic stress, while enhancing the production

of reducing power and precursors required for pDNA synthesis [21, 39].

There are several ways to redirect carbon flux to PP pathway, either by gene overexpression or knockout, illustrated schematically in Fig. 1.4. For instance, one approach would be the deletion of pyruvate kinase isoenzymes (*pykF* and *pykA* genes), since these enzymes catalyze the final step of glycolysis and in P⁺ cells *pykF* is upregulated. This strain exhibited up to a 4-fold increase in pDNA yield and decreased acetate production [15, 39, 53].

Figure 1.4: Potential gene overexpressions and knockout to improve pDNA production in *E. coli*, targeting glycolysis, PP pathway and TCA cycle. (A) Overexpression of the *zwf* and *rpiA* genes increases PP flux, allowing for increased nucleotide synthesis. Knockout of *pgi*, that redirects the carbon flux to the PP pathway. (B) Knockouts of genes *pykF* and *pykA* will reduce acetate formation, by directing PEP to the TCA cycle. Dark arrows represent high carbon flow in PP pathway and light arrows represent less formation of acetate and pyruvate. Abbreviations: G6P, glucose 6-phosphate; F6P, fructose 6-phosphate; FDP, fructose 1,6-diphosphate; G3P, glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate; PEP, phosphoenolpyruvate; OAA, oxaloacetate; MAL, malate; 6PGC, 6-phosphogluconate; RU5P, ribulose 5-phosphate; XU5P, xylulose 5-phosphate; R5P, ribose 5-phosphate; S7P, sedoheptulose 7-phosphate; E4P, erythrose 4-phosphate; PTS, phosphotransferase system. Adapted from [39].

Another strategy is the knockout of *fruR*, which encodes a transcriptional regulator involved in activating the TCA cycle enzymes and repressing the glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase gene (*zwf*) from the PP pathway. Therefore, its inactivation diverts flux from the TCA cycle, directing it instead to the PP pathway [15]. It was shown to increase pDNA yield under exponential feeding in fed-batch conditions. Another interesting target is the *rpiA* gene, from the PP pathway, which encodes for ribose-5-phosphate isomerase A. Thus, overexpressing this gene increases synthesis of ribose-5-phosphate, a nucleotide precursor. This showed a 3-fold increase in plasmid copy number [39, 53]. The overexpression of *zwf* has also been explored, which encodes for glucose 6-phosphate-1-dehydrogenase, involved in PP pathway. In a study, this resulted in an increased *E. coli* growth rate. The simultaneous overexpression of

zwf and *rpiA* appeared to increase volumetric pDNA yield, but not specific pDNA yield [53].

Gonçalves *et al.* (2013) identified another promising genetic target, the *pgi* gene, which encodes the enzyme phosphoglucose isomerase, catalyzing the conversion of glucose-6-phosphate into fructose-6-phosphate, the first step of glycolysis (Fig. 1.4A). Knockout of *pgi* prevents glucose-6-phosphate from entering glycolysis, therefore redirecting it toward the PP pathway, which enhances nucleotide synthesis and consequently pDNA production. However, glycolysis might still continue due to the generation of fructose-6-phosphate and glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate through erythrose 4-phosphate from the PP pathway. The *pgi*-deficient strain, designated GALG20, also with *endA* and *recA* knockout (MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* Δ *pgi*), produced up to 25-fold more pDNA than its parental strain, highlighting *pgi* as a highly promising target for further research and one of the key focal points of this master thesis [18, 46].

1.2.3.3 Gene knockout strategies

Gene knockout is a widely used strategy in strain engineering to improve metabolic traits by deactivating specific genes. These knockouts can be designed using a variety of *in vitro* techniques, with the most prominent being λ Red homologous recombination, suicide plasmid vector systems, and CRISPR/Cas9-based approaches. Other methods include zinc-finger nuclease and transcription activator-like effector protein nuclease technology (TALEN) [55].

The Red recombination method, also known as recombineering (homologous recombination mediated genetic engineering), was used in this work, with the method developed by Datsenko and Wanner (2000), standing out for its simplicity, efficiency, and widespread use in *E. coli*. This system allows for direct modification of a genome, independent of restriction sites, with the constructs designed at the base-pair level. It is based on three genes from the λ phage (Gam, Exo and Beta), and those proteins will mediate homologous recombination of linear DNA fragments with genes within the genome. Exo proteins degrade linear dsDNA from the 5' end, while Beta proteins bind the single stranded DNA (ssDNA) and promote annealing to the target gene. Appropriate access to DNA ends is granted by Gam, which inhibits the RecBCD exonuclease V from the host, to prevent degradation of the linear DNA [50, 55].

In the widely adopted Datsenko and Wanner (2000) method, these genes are expressed from the temperature-sensitive auxotrophic plasmid pKD46, under the control of an arabinose-inducible promoter. A PCR product carrying a kanamycin resistance gene with FRT sites (from plasmid pKD13), flanked by 36–50 bp homology arms, is introduced into cells harboring pKD46. Then, homologous recombination replaces the target gene with the resistance cassette [55].

To remove the Kan-cassette, a flippase (FLP) recombinase is expressed from the plasmid pCP20 and excises the resistance gene. This enzyme recognizes the FRT sites flanking the cassette, leaving behind a minimal genomic scar. Both pKD46 and pCP20 are easily cured by incubation at 37°C due to their temperature-sensitive replicons. This system has proven robust, with reports of over 40 successful

chromosomal disruptions without failure [50]. It is further explored in the Section 3.1.4, Fig. 3.1.

Another common method is the suicide plasmid vector system, which uses plasmids that cannot replicate in the host without specific replication factors. After transformation, gene knockout is achieved through two rounds of homologous recombination using bacterial *recA* pathways. After recombination, the suicide plasmid is rejected due its inability to replicate [55].

A more recent and powerful tool has been employed, the CRISPR/Cas9 system, which enables precise genome editing via targeted DNA cleavage. In *E. coli*, double-strand breaks introduced by Cas9 can be repaired via λ -Red-mediated homologous recombination with suitable repair templates and plasmids. The combination of CRISPR and Red recombination enhances editing efficiency and accuracy [55].

Together, these strategies offer effective tools for engineering bacterial strains, with Red recombination standing out as the most widely used, including in this work, due to its simplicity and efficiency.

1.2.4 Fermentation strategies

Although plasmid stability and copy number largely depend on the genetic makeup of the host and vector, they are also strongly influenced by cultivation conditions and medium composition. The goal is to optimize all of these parameters to maximize both the volumetric yield and specific yield of pDNA, while minimizing the manufacturing costs [12, 15, 21].

1.2.4.1 Cultivation methods and conditions

The fermentation process is influenced by cultivation parameters, such as temperature, dissolved oxygen and pH. Lower specific growth rates result in higher pDNA yield. Specifically, it is thought that plasmid copy number increases during the late exponential and early stationary phases of growth. Shake flask, batch and fed-batch technologies have been employed for this matter [56].

pDNA production studies performed in shake flasks are poorly predictive of large-scale culture behavior and strain performance. However, they remain valuable tools for preliminary screening of strains, assessing genetically modified variants, comparing multiple strains simultaneously, and evaluating different media compositions and component concentrations [21].

While batch cultivation is operationally simple, it typically results in low volumetric pDNA yields. In contrast, fed-batch strategies, where nutrients are supplied over time, enable tighter control of nutrient availability, keeping it synchronized with the oxygen transfer capacity and maintaining a more stable growth rate. In fact, it has been shown to achieve up to an 8-fold increase in specific pDNA yield and a 25-fold increase in volumetric yield compared to shake flask cultures [39, 56].

Oxygen transfer often becomes a limiting factor, particularly at larger scales, as increasing oxygen availability in bioreactors is technically challenging. This lack of oxygen leads to the production of acetate. The use of pressurized bioreactors has recently been proposed to ensure sufficient oxygen supply

to high-cell-density cultures [12].

Temperature control also plays a crucial role in pDNA production. For instance, pUC-based vectors can undergo plasmid amplification when the temperature is gradually increased from 30°C to 42°C at a rate of 0.4°C/min. Maintaining an initial temperature of 30°C helps reduce metabolic burden and cell growth rate, promoting better plasmid maintenance before induction. In fact, elevated pH coupled with reduced temperature has been shown to increase plasmid copy number [12, 40, 56].

1.2.4.2 Media type and composition

The type and source of nutrients used for *E. coli* cultivation have a significant impact on pDNA yield and growth rate, affecting production costs. With a careful medium optimization, it is possible to reach cell densities of more than 120 g/L [12].

Rich and complex media, for example, containing yeast extract and peptones, are easy to prepare and typically result in higher biomass accumulation, faster growth rates, and increased pDNA yields compared to chemically defined media, making them economically advantageous [18, 21]. However, defined media are preferred by regulatory authorities due to their reproducibility and batch-to-batch consistency. Additionally, defined media are more suitable for kinetic model development, since there is only one carbon source being consumed, which can be easily monitored [21].

The nature of the carbon source plays a crucial role in fermentation performance and pDNA production. Glucose is typically the preferred carbon source for bacterial growth. However, in *E. coli*, its metabolism often results in acetate accumulation through overflow metabolism or mixed-acid fermentation, particularly when the maximum oxygen transfer capacity of the bioreactor is reached. Alternatively, glycerol can be used as a carbon source, since it generally leads to lower acetate levels and higher specific pDNA yields compared to glucose [21].

Acetate formation is highly strain-dependent and influenced by plasmid characteristics, medium composition, and culture strategy. To overcome these limitations, metabolic engineering strategies have been explored, such as engineering strains with optimized glucose uptake and reduced acetate formation, like the GALG20 strain, or adopting mixed carbon source approaches that combine glucose and glycerol during fermentation, balancing growth and pDNA productivity [21].

The carbon-to-nitrogen (C:N) ratio of the medium is another critical factor influencing pDNA yield. O’Kennedy *et al.* (2000) reported that an optimal ratio of 2.78 mol C/mol N maximized plasmid production [57]. The nitrogen source itself is equally important, as a combination of glutamate and ammonium chloride at optimized concentrations has been shown to significantly enhance pDNA yield. Moreover, optimizing complex nitrogen sources, such as yeast extract and peptones, can promote balanced *E. coli* growth and maintain high plasmid productivity [12].

Another strategy to boost pDNA yield involves inducing amino acid starvation. Hofmann *et al.* (1990) demonstrated that in *arg*-deficient *E. coli* strains, pDNA yield increased up to 10-fold following complete

depletion of arginine [12, 58]. Although this method is simple to apply and easily scalable, it requires supplementation of specific amino acids and precise timing of their depletion, which adds cost and process complexity [12].

While the optimization of these parameters is challenging, their combined fine-tuning can result in markedly higher pDNA quality and yield.

1.2.5 Plasmid DNA Structural Variants

During pDNA production and manufacturing, maintaining product quality is critical, particularly for therapeutic uses. Quality control extends beyond concentration and purity assessments to evaluating isoform distribution, reflecting the efficiency of upstream and downstream processes [59, 60].

Plasmids can exist in several topological isoforms, SC, Open Circular (OC), and linear DNA, and their relative abundance is a Critical Quality Attribute (CQA), influencing biological activity and regulatory compliance. Their relative distribution varies with the replication state, the growth phase at the time of sampling and the shear stress caused by the purification process [61]. According to the FDA, pDNA-based vaccines are recommended to contain at least 80% of the SC isoform, since it exhibits superior transfection efficiency and biological activity compared to other forms, and is more resistant to enzymatic degradation, allowing a greater amount to reach the nucleus of the target cell [59, 60, 62].

The SC form is a covalently closed circular DNA structure characterized by “self-coiling” of the molecule. This conformation arises from helical stresses introduced by topoisomerases, which add or remove twists during the circularization of DNA. Degradation of SC pDNA can be initiated enzymatically, through strand nicking, or chemically, for example, by free radical oxidation. A single-strand nick releases the helical tension and generates the OC form. A localized double-strand break produces the linear isoform, such as that induced by restriction endonucleases. In purified preparations of pDNA, the OC form is typically the predominant initial degradation product derived from SC pDNA [60].

In addition to these canonical isoforms, multimeric plasmid forms, or concatemers, can arise during replication through homologous recombination, resulting in dimers, trimers, or higher-order structures. These forms have the same sequence but a different physical arrangement, forming tandem repeats of the same plasmid molecule. As a consequence, they can reduce the number of functional copies per cell and may complicate manufacturing consistency and downstream performance. Multimer formation can be influenced by plasmid-encoded, chromosomal, and environmental factors. However, in most bacterial strains used for large-scale production, which are deficient in recombination genes, multimer formation is minimized. Interestingly, these multimeric forms may also hold potential for biopharmaceutical applications, as the presence of multiple gene copies can enhance transfection efficiency compared to the monomeric form [12, 63, 64, 65].

Understanding isoform heterogeneity, including multimer formation, is therefore essential to ensure plasmid stability, process control, and compliance with regulatory standards.

1.2.6 Regulatory Considerations in plasmid DNA manufacturing

The large-scale manufacturing of pDNA is strictly regulated under GMP conditions to ensure the consistency, safety, and reproducibility of the product. pDNA with GMP-grade might be either a starting material or an Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) and should be manufactured in certified facilities operating under validated and auditable systems [66].

It is also recommended to avoid antibiotic-resistance marker genes in clinical plasmids, as they cause a metabolic burden for the host and raise safety concerns, including the risk of spreading antibiotic resistance genes by HGT to intestinal bacteria, which may also cause inflammatory responses and reduce transfection efficiency [67].

According to current FDA guidance, pDNA must originate from a qualified and traceable microbial cell bank, with complete documentation of its genotype, origin, and maintenance records. All of the materials, process controls, and documentation should have full traceability, from fermentation to final purification, and all the critical steps must be validated to ensure reproducibility. Once manufactured, quality control testing of each batch confirms identity, concentration, isoform purity, and efficacy [27].

CQA define the measurable characteristics that determine quality, safety, and efficacy, including the proportion of SC isoform, host-cell or microbial contaminants, concentration, and endotoxin levels. To maintain a stable isoform distribution, a careful optimization of fermentation conditions and controlled purification processes are required. The standardized workflow relies on validated methods [68, 69].

The main regulatory agencies have also established guidelines for pDNA use and production, such as the FDA, with the guidance “Recommendations for Microbial Vectors Used for Gene Therapy”, and the European Medicines Agency (EMA), with the guideline “Quality, Non-Clinical, and Clinical Aspects of Gene Therapy Medicinal Products”. These regulations highlight genetic stability, process traceability, and impurity control as critical pillars for achieving compliant manufacturing [27, 70, 71].

1.2.7 Digital Twins in plasmid DNA manufacturing

The main challenge in pDNA production is efficiently producing the active SC isoform required to meet regulatory standards [68]. Regulatory agencies expect robust, science-based evidence of process understanding and control before market authorization [38]. Following the Quality by Design (QbD) framework, process characterization and optimization are essential to identify and monitor Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) and their impact on Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs), ensuring reproducible product quality before scale-up [68]. Advanced solutions in pDNA manufacturing, such as high-density fed-batch fermentation and optimized downstream purification, provide robust data streams for Design of Experiments (DoE) methodologies, establishing correlations that can drive further process optimization through kinetic modelling approaches [12].

The transition toward Industry 4.0 has introduced digitalization and automation into biomanufacturing, with the goal of increasing efficiency, predictability, throughput, and scalability, conserving resources,

and minimizing environmental impact. A fundamental principle in this scope is mapping the physical space in a digital object via a digital twin, which is a virtual replica of a process that mirrors its physical counterpart in real-time and *in silico*. This approach integrates data analytics, Process Analytical Technologies (PAT), computational modeling, machine learning, the Internet of Things (IoT) and automation. By combining these, it is possible to simulate and optimize processes in a risk-free environment, improving control, facilitating autonomous decision-making, reducing costs, and meeting regulatory standards. From a mechanistic perspective, digital twins consist of a two-way data flow between the physical system and its digital counterpart (Fig. 1.5). This could enable real-time release testing and autonomous control strategies, marking a key step toward fully digital and intelligent bioprocessing [72]. In pDNA manufacturing, digital twins can model upstream fermentation and downstream purification steps, allowing *in silico* prediction of pDNA yield, SC ratio, and impurity levels [72, 73].

In bioreactor technology, digital twins constitute a progression from the integration of PAT, shifting manufacturing from end-point testing to real-time monitoring and control. Virtual replicas of bioreactors allow continuous prediction and fine-tuning of process parameters in real-time such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and nutrient supply, critical for optimizing cell growth and productivity [72]. Recent European initiatives highlight this evolution. The DIG4BIO project focuses specifically on the digitalization of *E. coli*-based pDNA manufacturing. In parallel, the CoDiBio project targets continuous and digitalized bioprocessing of pDNA using hybrid modeling and real-time analytics [74, 75].

It is reasonable to anticipate that digitizing pDNA production could yield improvements comparable to those achieved in other biomanufacturing areas, upstream throughput gains of 15-30 %, downstream efficiency increases up to 60%, and substantial enhancements in resource efficiency and process robustness, thus advancing decision-making, efficiency and sustainability [73].

Figure 1.5: Schematic representation of a digital twin, comprising a physical asset with real-time monitoring and offline-generated data that mirrors it. Retrieved from [72].

2. Background and objectives

Over recent years, the global demand for pDNA has risen dramatically, primarily due to the continuous emergence and expansion of cell and gene therapies and immunotherapies, which are revolutionizing the treatment of previously untreatable diseases. These therapies depend on the scalable and reliable production of pDNA for clinical trials and ultimately commercialization, increasing the demand for processes capable of delivering both high quality and high quantity of pDNA. However, large-scale manufacturing remains a major bottleneck, due to challenges in reproducibility and compliance with GMP standards, delaying regulatory approval [38].

Moreover, regulatory agencies expect manufacturers to present robust, science-based evidence of process understanding and control before progressing to market authorization [38]. Those can be achieved through modeling approaches, such as kinetic models, and by implementing QbD and PAT frameworks, hence supporting risk assessment, process optimization and continuous improvement [76]. For this purpose, chemically defined media are recommended, as their reproducibility and well-defined composition facilitate process modeling and correlation of nutrient dynamics with pDNA production.

In this context, digitalization of biomanufacturing processes, particularly by using digital twins, integrating QbD and PAT principles, emerged as a powerful strategy to enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and enable real-time monitoring, control and optimization of bioprocesses. This accelerates regulatory approval and transition toward smart biomanufacturing, overcoming current bottlenecks [68, 77].

However, the development of accurate and reliable digital twins depends on the availability of high quality and robust experimental data to build and validate predictive models, which should capture biological mechanisms and observed variability [77].

Moreover, to maximize pDNA yields, several factors must be considered. In addition to scale-up issues, low yields and plasmid instability also complicate large-scale plasmid manufacturing. Therefore, although the growth medium and fermentation conditions are important, starting with a robust, high-producing pDNA strain is essential. A promising and relatively unexplored approach is to engineer *E. coli* strains with enhanced pDNA production capacity, through strain engineering, selecting genes involved in central carbon metabolism, given the metabolic burden observed during pDNA production.

In this context, Gonçalves *et al.* (2013) have developed the GALG20 strain, by knocking out the *pgi* gene, thus redirecting carbon flux to the PP pathway, reducing acetate formation and enhancing synthesis of nucleotide and amino acid precursors. GALG20 produced up to 25-fold more pDNA than its parental strain in glucose, highlighting it as a promising strain for further investigation [18].

2.1 Aim of the study

In this light, the main goal of this thesis is to generate a solid and robust experimental dataset to serve as a starting point for a kinetic model for pDNA production, enabling proper parameter estimation and ensuring strong model performance. This work also aims to establish the basis for a future DoE approach, with multiple variables varying simultaneously, to determine patterns and correlations that can drive further process optimization. Therefore, the future model should contribute to a deeper understanding of the biological mechanisms underlying pDNA production, ultimately supporting the future development of a digital twin for pDNA production in a fermentation system in *E. coli* [21].

The secondary objectives of this thesis are:

- To construct the MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* strain with the λ Red recombination system, described by Datsenko and Wanner (2000), allowing direct comparison with the engineered GALG20 strain [50];
- To perform a comparative analysis in order to evaluate the impact of strain genotype, focusing on the high-yield GALG20 strain, and also plasmid burden and medium composition (including carbon source and amino acid supplementation) on cell growth, pH, substrate consumption, acetate formation, and pDNA yield and quality.

Experimentally, this involved performing comparative growth experiments to evaluate the performance of three strains, parental (MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*), engineered (GALG20), and control (DH5 α), with and without pDNA in shake flasks using the selected chemically defined media. DH5 α is widely used for delivering reproducible and stable results. The selected plasmid was pVAX1GFP, which carries a kanamycin resistance marker, the only antibiotic approved by regulatory agencies for pDNA production [21]. pVAX1-GFP was used solely as a model plasmid, since GFP has no therapeutic interest.

The media adapted from Listner *et al.* (2006), containing glucose or glycerol, and the medium designed by Wang *et al.* (2001) were selected [2, 78]. The latter induces amino acid starvation, enabling the evaluation of its impact on pDNA production, supposedly beneficial for pDNA yield [12]. Substrate consumption and metabolite formation were monitored via High-performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), and pDNA production was assessed by determining its yield, quality and isoform ratio.

Overall, this work aims to generate the experimental foundation required to support future model development and the creation of a digital twin for pDNA manufacturing, providing insights into optimizing strain performance and fermentation processes for industrial biopharmaceutical applications.

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Construction of MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* strain

For the comparative analysis of GALG20 and its parental strain, it was necessary to produce the MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* strain, by knocking out the *recA* gene using the λ Red recombination system, described by Datsenko and Wanner (2000) [50].

3.1.1 Bacterial strains and plasmids

E. coli MG1655 Δ *endA* (F⁻ λ *ilvG rfb-50 rph1* Δ *endA*), was constructed by Gonçalves *et al.* (2013) and it was used for the *recA* gene knockout. The *endA* gene knockout previously performed in this strain was carried out with P1 transduction, as described in Gonçalves *et al.* (2013) [18].

The plasmids used in the λ Red recombination system were pKD46, pCP20 and pKD13, low copy-number plasmids, represented in Fig. A.2. The pKD46 plasmid is temperature-sensitive and comprises the λ Red recombination system, (including genes β , γ and *exo* from phage I), with the control of an arabinose inducible promoter, and an ampicillin resistance gene [79]. The pCP20 contains the yeast *flp* recombinase gene and carries chloramphenicol and ampicillin resistance genes. It displays temperature-sensitive replication and FLP synthesis is induced also by temperature [80]. The pKD13 plasmid carries the Kan-cassette (kanamycin resistance gene) flanked by FRT sites. This cassette is commonly used in molecular engineering as a selectable marker to identify successful genetic modifications [81]. The characteristics from these plasmids are summarized in Table 3.1. These plasmids were replicated in DH5 α cells according to the conditions described in Section 3.1.2, with the appropriate antibiotic according to the plasmid. Then, plasmid purification was achieved using the High Pure Plasmid Isolation Kit (Roche). Purified plasmids were stored at -20°C and plasmid concentration was determined with Nanodrop Spectrophotometer (Nanovue Plus, GE Healthcare).

3.1.2 Media and growth conditions

For plasmid amplification, *E. coli* DH5 α (Invitrogen) was used. The inoculum was grown in 5 mL of liquid LB medium (Luria Bertani Broth, 20 g/L, NZYTech), with ampicillin (25 μ g/mL, NZYTech) for DH5 α cells harboring pKD46 and pCP20 or kanamycin (25 μ g/mL, Merck) for DH5 α cells harboring pKD13, at 250 rpm and 30°C for pKD46 and pCP20 and 37°C for pKD13. Cells were grown overnight and harvested by centrifugation.

When necessary, *E. coli* cells were grown in LB agar (2%, Sigma Aldrich) plates, at 30°C or 37°C (depending on the plasmid), supplemented with the appropriate antibiotic, and stored at 4°C.

Cells banks of DH5 α with these plasmids were made in glycerol 20% (v/v) final concentration and final volume of 100 μ L, and stored at -80°C.

Table 3.1: Main characteristics of the plasmids used in the λ Red recombination system protocol.

Plasmids	Size (bp)	Construct	Reference
pKD46	6329	oriR101 w/repA101ts, Amp ^R , Gam-beta-exo proteins under the control of arabinose inducible promoter	[79]
pCP20	9332	FLP ⁺ , λ cl857 ⁺ , λ p _R Rep ^{ts} , Cm ^R , Amp ^R	[80]
pKD13	3434	oriR6Kgamma, Kan ^R flanked by FRT sites, Amp ^R	[81]

3.1.3 Competent cells and transformation

Chemically competent *E. coli* MG1655 Δ *endA* cells were prepared using cells grown until an Optical Density (OD) at 600 nm of 1, in a 100 mL shake flask with 20 mL of LB medium, at 37°C and 250 rpm. The culture was inoculated with an overnight pre-inoculum to an initial OD_{600nm} of 0.1. Freshly grown cells were harvested by centrifugation (1000 g, 10 min, 4°C) and resuspended in 2 mL of chilled TSS solution (which contained 20 g/L of LB medium, 5% DMSO, 50 mM MgCl₂, 10% PEG 8000 (w/v), pH=6.5). After a 10-minute incubation on ice, 100 μ L aliquots were prepared and stored at -80°C.

For transformation by heat shock, 100 μ L of chemically competent cells were mixed with 10 ng of the plasmid used in each experiment and incubated on ice for 30 min. The mixture was then submitted to 42°C for 60 s, followed by immediate incubation on ice for 2 min. Afterwards, the cells were resuspended in 1 mL of LB medium and incubated for 1 h at the appropriate temperature for the plasmid used in each experiment, at 250 rpm. Finally, the cells were plated on LB agar, with the appropriate antibiotic and incubated overnight at the correct temperature, depending on the plasmid used.

3.1.4 Gene knockout strategy

The knockout strategy using λ Red recombinase system allows for direct modification of *E. coli* genome, following four main steps, schematized in Fig. 3.1.

During the process, the kanamycin resistance cassette (Kan-cassette) and the flanking FRT sites are both amplified from the pKD13 plasmid, while the primers were designed to include regions of homology (H1 and H2) within the target gene (*recA* in this case) in the *E. coli* genome. These homology regions enable the recombination event in which the *recA* gene is replaced by the FRT-flanked Kan-cassette, mediated by the phage λ Red recombination system. Subsequently, the Kan-cassette can be excised by FLP recombinase, which recognizes the FRT sites, leaving a single scar in the genome.

Kan-cassette construction and amplification:

The first step consisted of producing the Kan-cassette. The insertion cassette contains the Kan^R, flanked by FRT, and homology regions (adjacent to the FRT) from the gene to be disrupted (H1 and H2), as schematized in Fig. 4.3. For this purpose, primers for PCR amplification were designed using the tool ApE. The DNA sequence of the *recA* gene was consulted to design primers that anneal to

Figure 3.1: Recombineering for gene disruption, via λ Red recombinase system. P1 and P2 refer to priming sites and H1 and H2 refer to homology regions. Retrieved from [50].

regions before and after the gene (flanking it), enabling homologous recombination [82]. The primers must contain around 20 nucleotides that correspond to the FRT sites, and around 60 nucleotides of the homology region from the target gene. Bearing this in mind, forward and reverse primers were designed, and their sequences and characteristics are listed in Table 3.2.

Subsequently, a PCR amplification was conducted, with pKD13 and the designed primers, to produce and amplify the Kan-cassette. The reaction mixture consisted of 10 ng of pKD13, 10 μ M of each primer and 1x KOD Hot Start Master Mix (Merck Millipore) and completed with PCR-grade water to a final volume of 20 μ L. The KOD Hot Start Master Mix contained a DNA polymerase with proofreading activity, highly accurate for cloning. The PCR program consisted of: initial denaturation for 3 min at 95°C, followed by 35 cycles of 1 min at 95°C, 1 min at 55°C or 60°C (to assess which temperature results in optimal primer annealing) and a final extension step of 1 min at 70°C. The PCR product was analysed by gel electrophoresis, as described in 3.2.9. After confirming that a single band was obtained, with the expected plasmid size, the PCR product was purified using the NZYGelpure kit (NZYtech), and the concentration was determined using NanoDrop Spectrophotometer (NanoVue Plus, GE Healthcare). When additional non-specific bands were identified after the PCR, the sample was re-analyzed on a 1% agarose gel stained with 0.5 μ g/mL of SYBR Safe DNA Gel Stain (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The Kan-cassette band was excised from the gel with appropriate tools and purified with the NZYGelpure kit, for direct purification from an agarose gel, and subsequently quantified as previously described. Finally, the purified plasmid was stored at -20°C.

Transformation of the λ Red recombinase-expressing strain:

The next step consisted of transforming the selected strain with λ Red recombinase. For that, *E. coli*

MG1655 $\Delta endA$ competent cells were transformed with the plasmid pKD46, according to the protocol described in Section 3.1.3. Since pKD46 is temperature sensitive, the cells were incubated at 30°C in the recovery step in order to express the λ Red recombinase and then grown in LB agar plates at the same temperature with ampicillin, to select successfully transformed cells. Some of the resulting colonies were picked and grown in 5 mL of LB medium with 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of ampicillin. pDNA was purified and analyzed in a gel to confirm the presence of pKD46. Positive clones were used to prepare cell banks, as previously described in Section 3.1.2.

Table 3.2: List of the primers used for *recA* gene knockout. F and R correspond to forward and reverse primers, respectively.

Primer name	Sequence (5' → 3')	Product size (bp)	T _m (°C)
recA_Kan_F	ATACTGTATGAGCATAACAGTATAATTG CTTCAACAGAACATATTGACTATCCGGTAT- TACgtgtaggctggagctgcttc	-	81°C
recA_Kan_R	TGATTCTGTCATGGCATATCCTTACAA CTTAAAAAAGCAAAGGGCCGCAGATGCGAC- CCtccgtcgacctgcagtt		89°C
recA_check_F	TCGTCAGGCTACTGCGTATGC	1414-1623 ^{1*}	55°C
recA_check_R	CGTCGCAGTTCTTGCTCACTG	149-389 ^{1**}	56°C
Kan_Cassette _cut_R	CATACGCTTGATCCGGCTAC	566-626 ¹	55.60°C

¹ Depending if the FRT regions are maintained during recombination.

* After recombination, with Kan-cassette

** After Kan-cassette removal

Recombination and Kan-cassette genomic integration:

In the third step, to promote the Kan-cassette integration, competent MG1655 $\Delta endA$ cells containing pKD46 were transformed with the Kan-cassette, with the protocol described in Section 3.1.3 with some modifications. During the induction of competence, the overnight inoculum contained 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of ampicillin to maintain pKD46 in the cells. Then, cells were grown until an OD_{600nm} of 0.6 in 30 mL of LB medium at 30°C with either 1 mM, 2 mM or 10 mM of L-arabinose to induce the expression of the λ Red recombinase genes. This OD_{600nm} corresponds to the mid-logarithmic growth phase, when the physiology of the cells is more amenable for DNA uptake. Cell division is fast, and with the replication fork actively working, the λ Red recombination machinery may access the target gene [83].

During transformation, 100 ng of the Kan-cassette were used, and cells were resuspended in 1 mL of LB medium and incubated for 3h at 30°C, 250 rpm, which is when recombination occurs. Afterwards, half of the culture volume was plated on LB agar supplemented with kanamycin 25 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mg}$ and incubated overnight at 37°C, to select recombinant colonies with the Kan-cassette. If no colonies were observed after 24h, the remaining culture volume would be incubated overnight at room temperature and plated

in the same conditions.

Colony PCR was then used to verify successful integration of the Kan-cassette and deletion of the *recA* sequence between the regions of homology. For PCR, primers were designed, and their sequences, product sizes, and T_m are included in Table 3.2 (*recA_check_F* and *recA_check_R*). They were designed using the ApE software, with a size of approximately 20 nucleotides and positioned slightly upstream of the beginning of the FRT1 included in the Kan-cassette and slightly downstream of the FRT2, from the *recA* sequence, respectively. Since the expected PCR product size with the Kan-cassette integration (1414 bp) was similar to the PCR product size with the original *recA* gene (1371 bp), the *Kan_Cassette_cut_R* primer was designed, binding near the middle of the Kan-cassette and generating a PCR product that is clearly distinguishable depending on whether recombination has been successful or not (approximately 600 bp of PCR product). The isolated colonies (around 10, to increase the likelihood of identifying one that had the Kan-cassette) were resuspended in 20 μL of PCR-grade water. Each colony PCR reaction mixture contained 5 μL of the resuspended colony, NZYtaq II 2x Green Master Mix (NZYtech), 10 μL of each primer, completed with PCR-grade water to a final volume of 25 μL . The cycling conditions were: initial denaturation for 3 min at 95°C, followed by 30 cycles of 30 s at 94°C, 30 s at 56°C (optimal temperature for annealing of both primers) and 30 s at 72°C, and a final extension step of 10 min at 72°C. The PCR product sample was run on a 1% agarose gel, as described in section 3.2.9.

As an additional strategy to assess Kan-cassette integration, the colony PCR product was digested with the restriction enzyme BglII, which recognizes the sequence 5'-AGATCT-3'. Since this site occurs only once in the Kan-cassette, successful integration will reveal two fragments, of approximately 537 and 1026 bp. For the colony PCR, the primers *recA_check_F* and *recA_check_R* were used. Following that, the PCR product was mixed with 0.5 μL of BglII (Promega), 1x buffer D (Promega), and completed with PCR-grade water, for a final volume of 30 μL . The digestion mixture was incubated at 37°C for 1h. One microgram of pKD13 was also digested, as a positive control to assess enzyme activity. Afterwards, the digestion product was purified using the NZYGelpure kit (NZYtech), for direct purification of PCR products, and analyzed on an agarose gel, to verify the restriction patterns, as previously described.

When recombination was successful, the positive clones were plated on LB agar, using the streak plate method, at 37°C, to ensure curing of pKD46. Without the appropriate antibiotic and upon temperature increase, pKD46 is eliminated from the cells, which is desirable to prevent unwanted recombination. Positive colonies were picked from LB agar plates and used to inoculate 5 mL of LB medium, incubated at 37°C and 250 rpm overnight. These cultures were plated on LB agar, supplemented with ampicillin, at 37°C, to confirm the pKD46 elimination and, therefore, the loss of ampicillin resistance. Cell banks were stored at -80°C, prepared as previously described in Section 3.1.2.

Kan-cassette elimination:

Finally, the last step involved eliminating the Kan-cassette using pCP20, an FLP expression plasmid. For this objective, cell banks from cultures that did not grow on ampicillin plates were used to inoculate 5 mL of LB medium, incubated at 37°C and 250 rpm overnight. Then, MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*::Kan^R cells were made competent and transformed with the pCP20 plasmid, with the protocol described in Section 3.1.3 with minor modifications. During transformation, the cells were incubated for 1h at 30°C and 250 rpm, since pCP20 is temperature-sensitive. These were plated on LB agar, supplemented with ampicillin, at 30°C overnight, also due to the plasmid's temperature sensitivity. Afterwards, ampicillin-resistant colonies were picked and plated on LB agar, at 43°C, to induce FLP recombinase activity, to remove the Kan-cassette, and to cure all helper plasmids used.

Then, colonies were picked, resuspended in Milli-Q water and plated on three different plates, at 37°C overnight: LB agar, LB agar supplemented with ampicillin and LB agar supplemented with kanamycin. Colonies from the LB agar plate were replated on LB agar plates at 37°C overnight, to further confirm the absence of the helper plasmids. Another colony PCR with the same procedure described above was performed with 5 μ L of the resuspended cells, to ensure Kan-cassette removal, with only the *recA* scar present, without mixed colonies. The primers used were *recA*_check.F and *recA*_check.R. After, selected colonies were grown in 5 mL of LB medium, at 37°C and 250 rpm overnight. Finally, MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* cell banks were prepared and stored at -80°C, as previously described in Section 3.1.2. Subsequently, the *recA* knockout was also confirmed by sequencing, by Stab Vida.

3.2 Growth Experiments

3.2.1 Bacterial strains and plasmid

For the growth experiments, the strains used are described in Table 3.3. The DH5 α was purchased from Invitrogen and the original MG1655 was kindly given by the Prather Lab, MIT. The strain MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* was constructed in this study starting from MG1655 Δ *endA*, through λ Red recombination system, as described in Section 3.1. GALG20 was constructed by Gonçalves *et al.* (2013). The *endA* knockout was carried out with P1 transduction, and the *recA* knockout was performed with the λ Red recombination system, as in this study [18].

MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* was transformed with pVAX1-GFP, following the protocol described above in Section 3.1.3 using kanamycin as the antibiotic. To confirm successful transformation, these cells were plated on LB agar plates with kanamycin. Seed banks were prepared from single colonies and inoculated in LB medium supplemented with kanamycin. Cultures were grown to mid-exponential phase at 37°C, 250 rpm (Orbital Corning LSE Benchtop Shaking Incubator), after which cells were harvested, purified for pDNA, and analyzed by gel electrophoresis. Once the expected pDNA size was confirmed, seed banks were prepared and frozen at -80°C, in 20% (v/v) final concentration of glycerol. DH5 α and

GALG20 harboring pVAX1-GFP were used from frozen cell banks.

The plasmid used was the pVAX1-GFP (3697 bp), represented in Fig. A.1. It was derived from pVAX1LacZ (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) according to the protocol described by Azzoni *et al.* (2007) [18, 19]. In this study, pVAX1-GFP was used solely as a model plasmid, since GFP has no therapeutic interest. The sequence of this plasmid is presented in the Appendix.

Table 3.3: *E. coli* strains used in the growth experiments and their respective genotypes.

<i>E. coli</i> strain	Genotype	Reference
DH5 α	F ⁻ Φ 80 <i>lacZ</i> Δ M15 Δ (<i>lacZYA-argF</i>)U169 <i>recA1 endA1</i> <i>hsdR17</i> (<i>r_k⁻, m_k⁺</i>) <i>phoA supE44 thi-1 gyrA96 relA1</i>	Invitrogen
MG1655 Δ <i>endA</i> Δ <i>recA</i>	F ⁻ λ <i>ilvG rfb-50 rph1</i> Δ <i>endA</i> Δ <i>recA</i>	This study
GALG20	MG1655 Δ <i>endA</i> Δ <i>recA</i> Δ <i>pgi</i>	[18]

3.2.2 PCR for genotype verification

Before starting the growth experiments, it is crucial to confirm that the GALG20 strain indeed contained the *endA*, *recA* and *pgi* knockouts, as expected. Primers were designed to anneal within each gene, slightly upstream of FRT1 and slightly downstream of FRT2, the sites where the knockouts were introduced. The characteristics of the designed primers are presented in Table 3.4. MG1655 Δ *endA* was used as a positive control for *endA* absence and as a negative control for the remaining genes. *Actinobacillus succinogenes*, a wild-type bacterial strain, was used as a negative control for *endA*, *recA* and *pgi* verification. PCR was performed using cells from frozen WCB, which were mixed with NZYTaq II 2 \times Green Master Mix, 10 μ L of each primer, completed with PCR-grade water to a final volume of 25 μ L.

Table 3.4: List of the primers used for GALG20 genotype verification. Product size corresponds to the deletion scar of each gene or the original gene size. F and R correspond to forward and reverse primers, respectively.

Primer name	Sequence (5' \rightarrow 3')	Product size (bp)	Tm ($^{\circ}$ C)
endA_check_F	CGTCTATCGCTGTGTTCA	\sim 251*	46 $^{\circ}$ C
endA_check_R	GGTTCAGGATGATAAATGCG	959**	50 $^{\circ}$ C
recA_check_F	TCGTCAGGCTACTGCGTATGC	149-389* ¹	55 $^{\circ}$ C
recA_check_R	CGTCGCAGTTCTTGCTCACTG	1371**	56 $^{\circ}$ C
check_pgi_F	AATGCTTCACTGCGCTAAGG	\sim 139*	55.80 $^{\circ}$ C
check_pgi_R	CGTCGGCATTGTTATTAAGG	1949**	51.55 $^{\circ}$ C

¹ Depending if the FRT are maintained during recombination.

* Deletion scar size ** Original gene size

The cycling conditions were: initial denaturation for 3 min at 95 $^{\circ}$ C, followed by 30 cycles of 30 s at

94°C, 30 s at 50°C, 55°C and 56°C, optimal temperatures for *endA*, *pgi* and *recA* primers, respectively, and 30 s at 72°C, and a final extension step of 10 min at 72°C. The PCR product sample was run on a 1% agarose gel, as described in section 3.2.9.

3.2.3 Media preparation

The growth experiments were conducted using two different chemically defined media, adapted from the formulation described by Listner *et al.* (2006) and designed by Wang *et al.* (2001) [2, 78]. In both cases, the same medium was used for both the inoculum and the production phase.

The medium based on Listner *et al.* (2006) is composed of the basal media and the Seed Supplement Solution (SSS), in Milli-Q water, and the Trace Element Solution (TES), in 1.2 N of HCl (Riedel-de Haen). The basal media contained (in final concentration): 7 g/L of KH₂PO₄ (PanReac), 7 g/L of K₂HPO₄ (PanReac), 6 g/L of (NH₄)₂SO₄ (Fisher BioReagents), 5 g/L of monosodium glutamate (Sigma Aldrich), and 20 g/L of glucose (Scharlau) or 10 g/L of glycerol (Fisher BioReagents). When studying the influence of substrate concentration, glucose or glycerol was used at 5, 10 or 20 g/L. The pH of the basal media was adjusted to 7.2, with a 30% NaOH solution (Fisher Chemicals) and sterilized by filtration through a 0.22 μm membrane with a vacuum pump (Lbx instruments, V10 series). The SSS at 8.3 mL/L and the TES at 1 mL/L, prepared separately from the basal medium, were added after sterilization [78].

The SSS contained 24 g/L of thiamine-HCl (Sigma Aldrich) and 240 g/L of MgSO₄·7H₂O (LabChem). Their concentrations in the final mixture were 0.2 g/L and 2 g/L, respectively. The TES, prepared in 1.2 N of HCl, contained: 27 g/L of FeCl₃·6H₂O (Fluka), 2 g/L of ZnCl₂ (Sigma Aldrich), 2 g/L of CoCl₂·6H₂O (Fluka), 2 g/L of Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O (Merck), 1 g/L of CaCl₂·2H₂O (Panreac), 1.3 g/L of CuCl₂·2H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich), and 0.5 g/L of H₃BO₃ (Fisher Chemicals). Their concentrations in the final mixture were 0.027 g/L of FeCl₃·6H₂O, 0.002 g/L of ZnCl₂, 0.002 g/L of CoCl₂·6H₂O, 0.002 g/L of Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, 0.001 g/L of CaCl₂·2H₂O, 0.0013 g/L of CuCl₂·2H₂O and 0.0005 g/L of H₃BO₃. The medium composition is in line with other chemically defined media used for *E. coli* cultivation [78].

As for the medium designed by Wang *et al.* (2001), a simplified stoichiometric model was used to optimize nutrient composition for pDNA production in *E. coli*. This approach accounted for the contribution of each nutrient in the production of cell mass and plasmid synthesis, as an alternative to the complex analysis of metabolic flux distribution. Amino acids were included, since amino acid starvation has been shown to improve pDNA replication. Thus, the medium included: 1.240 g/L of aspartate (Alfa Aesar), 1.152 g/L of glutamine (Sigma Aldrich), 0.378 g/L of glycine (NZYtech), 0.111 g/L of histidine (Sigma-Aldrich), 0.693 g/L of leucine (Sigma-Aldrich), 0.030 g/L of tryptophan (Alfa Aesar), 10 g/L of glucose, 12.8 g/L of Na₂HPO₄·7H₂O (Merck), 3 g/L of KH₂PO₄, 0.5 g/L of NH₄Cl (Panreac), 0.24 g/L of MgSO₄ (Alfa Aesar), and 0.004 g/L of thiamine-HCl. The pH of the media was also adjusted to 7.2, using a 30% NaOH solution and subsequently sterilized by filtration through a 0.22 μm membrane with a vacuum pump [2].

For plasmid-producing cultures, kanamycin was added to the medium at a concentration of 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.

3.2.4 Growth conditions

The inoculum was prepared from half of a frozen WCB in 5 mL of basal media, supplemented with SSS and TES. For plasmid-producing cultures, kanamycin was added. It was grown overnight, at 37°C, 250 rpm. The following day, the inoculum was used to inoculate batch cultures in 100-mL shake flasks to an initial $\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$ of 0.1. The shake flasks contained 30 mL of basal media, supplemented with SSS and TES (and kanamycin for plasmid-producing cultures). For the other medium, 5 mL and 30 mL were used for the inoculum and production phase, respectively. Cultures were grown at 37°C and aerated by shaking at 250 rpm for 20 h or 24 h. Glucose or glycerol was used as the primary carbon source.

For each medium and carbon source, two growth experiments were performed: in the first, shake-flask cultures were monitored from 0 to 9h and again at 24h; in the second, they were allowed to grow until 10h and monitored from 10h to 20h. In most experiments, two replicates were prepared for each strain with and without pDNA, with a total of twelve shake flasks.

Biomass and pH were measured hourly. Samples were collected at 0h, 5h, 7h, 9h, 24h and 12h, 15h, 18h to quantify glucose/glycerol and acetate (600 μL), and at the same time points, excluding 0h, to quantify pDNA (1 mL). Samples were stored at -20°C until further processing.

For biomass monitoring, 100 μL were sampled, diluted 1:10 in Milli-Q water and $\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$ was measured with a UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Hitachi U-2000, Thermo Fisher Scientific). This wavelength is commonly used to estimate bacterial biomass since it minimizes interference from media components and biological molecules, while being scattered efficiently by bacterial cells. pH was measured directly from the shake flask culture, with a previously calibrated pH meter from Mettler Toledo E220.

3.2.5 Biomass quantification

To determine the biomass concentration, a correlation factor of 0.35 $\text{g}_{\text{DCW}}/\text{L}$ per $\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$ was applied to convert $\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$ values to Dry Cell Weight (DCW). It was calculated as an average of two values from other studies conducted in similar conditions [84, 85].

3.2.6 Metabolite quantification

To determine the concentration of glucose, glycerol and acetate, culture samples were centrifuged at 10000 g for 5 min at room temperature. The supernatant was mixed with an equal volume of H_2SO_4 (550 μL) and centrifuged under the same conditions. 1 mL of the resulting supernatant was transferred into an HPLC vial for analysis.

For the HPLC analysis, an ELITE La Chrom System (VWR Hitachi Autosampler L-2200) was used, equipped with: an HPLC pump (Hitachi LaChrom Elite L-2130), a column heater externally connected

(Croco-CIL 100-040-220P, 40 cm x 8 cm x 8 cm, 30-99°C), an Refractive Index (RI) detector for glucose/glycerol (L-2490, VWR Hitachi), an UV-Vis detector for acetate (L-2420, VWR Hitachi) and a Rezex ROA-Organic acid H+ 8% column (300 mm x 7.8 mm) at 65°C.

The HPLC analysis was carried out with 20 μ L of injection volume, using 5 mM of H₂SO₄ as the eluent. The column was maintained at 65°C, and the pump was operated at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min.

For standards preparation, a calibration curve from each metabolite was obtained. Serial dilutions of the metabolite stock solution were prepared with water and analyzed by HPLC. After calculating the area and retention time, the peak area was plotted against the metabolite concentration to obtain the calibration curve equation. For glucose, an 80 g/L stock solution was prepared and serially diluted, obtaining concentrations of 0.156, 0.3125, 0.625, 1.25, 2.5, 5, 10, 20 and 40 g/L. For acetate, a 20 g/L stock solution was used, obtaining concentrations of 0.039, 0.078, 0.156, 0.3125, 0.625, 1.25, 2.5, 5, 10 g/L for the calibration curve. For glycerol, a 40 g/L stock solution was prepared, resulting in concentrations of 0.078, 0.156, 0.3126, 0.625, 1.25, 2.5, 5, 10 and 20 g/L. All calibration samples were submitted to the same treatment as the culture samples before HPLC analysis.

Metabolite concentrations were determined using calibration curves by measuring the peak area corresponding to each metabolite's retention time, previously determined, and calculating the concentration from the respective calibration equation (Fig. A.4).

3.2.7 pDNA purification and quantification

For pDNA purification and quantification, 1 mL of the culture was collected. pDNA was purified using the High Pure Plasmid Purification Isolation Kit, from Roche. This protocol relies on the fact that, after alkaline lysis, where both pDNA and gDNA denature, pDNA renatures rapidly under neutralization and remains in the supernatant, while gDNA aggregates in the pellet. Then, after clearing the supernatant, pDNA binds selectively to the glass-fiber filter, in the presence of chaotropic salt (in this case, guanidine HCl). After purification, pDNA was quantified using a Nanodrop Spectrophotometer, with the double-stranded DNA section, determining the absorbance at 260 nm. pDNA was stored at 4°C. The volumetric yield of pDNA (mg/L) was calculated as the maximum amount of pDNA produced divided by the culture volume (30 mL). The specific yield of pDNA (mg/g_{DCW}) was determined by first converting the OD_{600nm} to DCW, in grams of biomass. The total amount of pDNA, in milligrams, present in 30 mL of culture, was then divided by the DCW, in grams of biomass.

3.2.8 Plasmid digestion

In order to verify if cells were producing the desired plasmid pVAX1-GFP, the pDNA sample was subjected to two enzymatic digestions. EcoRI (New England Biolabs) and BamHI (Promega) were selected. EcoRI, which recognizes the sequence 5'-GAATTC-3', will linearize the pVAX1-GFP, while BamHI recognizes the sequence 5'-GGATCC-3', which occurs twice in the plasmid, resulting in two

fragments of 730 bp and 2967 bp, as schematized in Fig. A.1.

For EcoRI digestion, 1000 ng of plasmid were mixed with 1 μ L of EcoRI, 1x CutSmart Buffer (New England Biolabs), and completed with PCR-grade water, for a final volume of 50 μ L. The digestion mixture was incubated at 37°C for 1h. As for BamHI digestion, 1000 ng of plasmid were mixed with 0.5 μ L of BamHI, 1x Buffer E (Promega), and completed with PCR-grade water, for a final volume of 25 μ L. The digestion mixture was incubated at 37°C for 3h, and analyzed in a gel electrophoresis.

3.2.9 Gel electrophoresis

When necessary, to assess plasmid isoforms or check restriction patterns, agarose gels were prepared with 1% (w/v) agarose (Thermo Fisher Scientific) in 1x tris-acetate-EDTA (TAE) buffer (40 mM Trisbase, 20 mM acetic acid and 1 mM EDTA, pH 8) and stained with a 1% ethidium bromide solution (Thermo Scientific), using NZYDNA Ladder III (NZYtech) (Fig. A.3) as a molecular weight marker. Each sample loaded in the gel contained 250 ng of pDNA mixed with a 6x gel loading dye (purple, New England BioLabs) or a 6X loading buffer, prepared with 40% (w/v) sucrose (Sigma Aldrich) and 0.25% (w/v) bromophenol blue (sodium salt, Sigma Aldrich), to increase sample density. Electrophoresis was performed in a horizontal electrophoresis tank, from VWR, and Amersham Electrophoresis Power Supply, EPS-301, for 1h at 120 V and 400 mA. Gel images were obtained with an Axygen[®] Gel Documentation system (GDBL-1000, Corning).

When the pDNA concentration was too low, the samples were concentrated with a DNA SpeedVac Concentrator (Savant DNA 120, Thermo Scientific) before proceeding to gel electrophoresis.

3.2.10 Isoform quantification

For isoform quantification, Fiji software was used, by measuring band densitometry. First, a rectangular selection around the first lane was marked by pressing Ctrl 1. The square was moved to the other lanes while pressing Ctrl 2 and after repeating this for all lanes, Ctrl 3 was pressed to produce graph plots. Lines were drawn to remove background and the “Wand” tool was used to obtain the densitometry measurements, which were further processed. All gel images were processed with this procedure.

To calculate the percentage of each isoform, the following calculation was used:

$$\% \text{ isoform}_A = \frac{\text{Area band, isoform A}}{\text{Area total, all isoforms}} \times 100$$

3.2.11 Statistical analysis

For each independent comparative growth, two replicates for each strain were prepared to ensure robustness, and the sample Standard Deviation (SD) was calculated. When possible, data are presented as mean \pm SD. When necessary, a two-tailed and two-sample Student's *t*-test was performed and differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Construction of MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* strain

For the comparative analysis of GALG20 with its parental strain, it was necessary to construct the MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* strain, by knocking out the *recA* gene using the λ Red recombination system, described by Datsenko and Wanner (2000) [50].

The intermediate and final knockout constructs were designed *in silico* to obtain the primers required for each step (Table 3.2). The helper plasmids necessary for the recombination process (pKD46, pKD13, and pCP20) were amplified in DH5 α cells, purified, and quantified, resulting in concentrations of 87.1 ng/ μ L for pKD13, 209.5 ng/ μ L for pKD46, and 141.7 ng/ μ L for pCP20. The A_{260}/A_{280} and A_{260}/A_{230} ratios were within the acceptable ranges for purified pDNA, and a distinct absorption peak at 260 nm confirmed high purity of the product.

4.1.1 Kan-cassette construction and amplification

The first step for the *recA* knockout was the PCR generation of a cassette with the Kan^R, as described in section 3.1.4. For the cassette amplification, the *recA*_Kan_F and *recA*_Kan_R primers were used (Table 3.2), with a homology sequence for *recA* gene and priming sites that anneal with the beginning and the end of the Kan-cassette, along with the pKD13 plasmid, which contained the Kan^R gene. The PCR product was analyzed in a 1% agarose gel, as shown in Fig. 4.1A. A clear band with an approximate size of 1400 bp was observed, corresponding to the expected fragment of 1414 bp, confirming successful amplification. Therefore, the gel electrophoresis was repeated using a less mutagenic stain, SYBR Safe, with higher cloning and transformation efficiencies. Since some faint bands were observed, likely due to nonspecific primer hybridization, the band corresponding to the Kan-cassette was excised, and the pDNA content was purified and quantified (13.8 ng/ μ L at 55°C and 18.8 ng/ μ L at 60°C), obtaining the Kan-cassette required for the subsequent step.

4.1.2 Transformation of the λ Red recombinase-expressing strain

In the second step, MG1655 Δ *endA* cells were transformed with the pKD46 plasmid, which encodes the proteins of the λ Red recombination system. The purified pDNA from the transformed cultures was analyzed on a 1% agarose gel (Fig. 4.1B). The plasmid pKD46 was included as a positive control. The pKD46 plasmid has a size of 6329 bp, but its SC isoform migrates faster on the gel and therefore appears smaller than its actual size. As depicted, all cultures contained the expected plasmid band, mainly in the SC isoform, confirming successful transformation, the good quality of pDNA and suitability of these cells for the subsequent step.

Figure 4.1: Agarose gels obtained to check for Kan-cassette construction and pKD46 transformation. A: Gel from the PCR amplification of the Kan-cassette. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 3 - Kan-cassette amplified at $T_{\text{annealing}} = 55^{\circ}\text{C}$; 7 - Kan-cassette amplified at $T_{\text{annealing}} = 60^{\circ}\text{C}$. In lanes 2, 4, 5 and 6 no sample was added. B: Gel from the purified pKD46 from transformed MG1655Δ*endA* cells. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 - purified pDK46 stock; 3 to 6 - purified pDK46 from different transformed cultures.

4.1.3 Kan-cassette genomic integration

After amplification and purification of the Kan-cassette, several unsuccessful attempts were made to promote recombination and insert the Kan-cassette in the MG1655Δ*endA*+pKD46 strain. Transformation seems to have been successful, since colonies were observed on LB agar plates supplemented with kanamycin, indicating the cells had acquired kanamycin resistance. However, through PCR, only a band corresponding to the size of the *recA* gene (1371 bp) was detected. The negative control MG1655Δ*endA* displayed a band of the same size, around 1400 bp, as shown in Fig. 4.2A.

Other attempts included plating the remaining culture volume incubated overnight, after the recovery step, but the results remained unchanged (data not shown). Since it was thought that the issue could be related to clear identification of a positive band, given that the Kan-cassette and the portion of the *recA* gene amplified have similar sizes (1414 bp and 1371 bp, respectively), the restriction enzyme BglIII was chosen for further confirmation. This enzyme cleaves the Kan-cassette only once, at the 5'AGATCT3' recognition site, resulting in two fragments (443 bp and 965 bp), as illustrated in Fig. 4.3. Moreover, the recovery time after transformation was increased to 3h.

Following this, the PCR was repeated, and the product was purified before digestion, to prevent potential contaminants from interfering with it. A positive control of the enzyme activity, digested pKD13, and a negative control, undigested pKD13, were included. Samples of the colonies containing the Kan cassette should result in two fragments after digestion (965 bp and 443 bp). As shown in Fig. 4.2B, no digestion in the colonies' lanes was observed, while the digested pKD13 displayed the expected size (3434 bp), and the undigested pKD13 lane displayed its isoforms, OC with higher molecular weight, and SC. This confirmed that the enzyme was active, indicating that the issue was not related to band visualization but rather to low recombination efficiency, highlighting the need to further optimize it.

Simultaneously, to reduce detection time of the Kan-cassette integration and simplify the workflow,

Figure 4.2: Agarose gels obtained from the colony PCR, used to check for Kan-cassette integration in MG1655 Δ *endA*+pKD46 cells. A - with *recA* check primers. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 - MG1655 Δ *endA* (negative control); 3 to 11 - different colonies of MG1655 Δ *endA* + Kan-Cassette ; 12 - MG1655 Δ *endA*; B - after purification and BglIII digestion. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 - digested pKD13; 3 - undigested pKD13; 4 to 11 - different colonies of MG1655 Δ *endA* + Kan-Cassette.

the primer Kan_cassette_cut_R was designed to produce amplification only when the Kan-cassette is present, using the *recA*.check.F primer as a forward pair (Table 3.2). The expected fragment size is approximately 626 bp, as the designed primer anneals in the middle of the cassette, as schematized in Fig. 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Kan-cassette used for *recA* knockout (1414 bp), with BglIII restriction site (dark purple) and Kan_Cassette_cut_R primer (purple) highlighted. In pink is shown the kanamycin resistance gene, in blue are the homology regions to *recA* gene (H1 and H2), in yellow are the priming sites, complementary to a portion of *recA*.Kan_F and *recA*.Kan_R, and in green are highlighted the FRT regions where the FLP recombinase will act to remove the resistance gene. Constructed with SnapGene.

Additionally, several parameters influencing recombination efficiency were optimized, since the problem appeared to be the lack of recombination. In this protocol, L-arabinose was used to induce recombination, as pKD46 contains an arabinose-inducible promoter controlling the expression of the γ , β , and *exo* genes of the λ Red recombination system. Therefore, the L-arabinose concentration was increased to 2 mM and 10 mM, a modification also described by Datsenko and Wanner (2000) [50]. Also, during the recovery step, the incubation time was increased to 3 h and the temperature was reduced to 30°C, since pKD46 is temperature-sensitive. Therefore, with lower temperature stabilizing it, gene expression might occur during the recovery step. Moreover, the amount of Kan-cassette DNA used for transfor-

mation was increased to 100 ng to enhance the probability of recombination. Finally, as observed in Fig. 4.4A, three recombinant colonies were obtained, with the 2 mM arabinose condition yielding a 10% recombination success rate (1 out of 10), and the 10 mM achieving a 18% success rate (2 out of 11). In the case of successful recombination, a band of 626 bp is expected. The Kan-cassette was used as a positive control, resulting in a ~ 600 bp band. Since on the lower lane the bands were slightly faint, a confirmation PCR was performed, which verified that the three colonies identified had successfully integrated the Kan-cassette into their genome (Fig. 4.4B) and, therefore, these were chosen to proceed with the experiment.

Figure 4.4: Agarose gels obtained from the colony PCR after the optimized recombination protocol, to check for successful Kan-cassette integration. The primers *recA_check_F* and *Kan_Cassette_cut_R* were used, resulting in a band of 626 bp if the Kan-cassette is present. A - recombination induced using different L-arabinose concentrations. Upper panel lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 - Kan-cassette (positive control); 3 to 12 - different colonies of *MG1655ΔendA* + Kan-cassette using 2 mM of L-arabinose. Lower panel lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 to 12 - different colonies of *MG1655ΔendA* + Kan-cassette using 10 mM of L-arabinose; B - confirmation of Kan-cassette integration. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 to 4 - positive colonies with Kan-cassette integration (3 from the upper panel and 2 and 3 from the lower panel from part A).

4.1.4 *recA* gene knockout

The last step of the recombineering strategy consisted of eliminating the Kan-cassette, by transforming *MG1655ΔendA::Kan^R* cells with the helper plasmid pCP20. This plasmid encodes the FLP recombinase, which excises the FRT-flanked Kan-cassette. A colony PCR was performed with six recombinant colonies obtained from the protocol with 2 mM of L-arabinose and six from the protocol with 10 mM of this inducer. If the excision was successful, the agarose gel should have a band with 389 bp, corresponding to the *recA* scar with the FRT sites. If not, the band at 1414 bp would indicate the presence of the Kan-cassette. As observed in Fig. 4.5, three outcomes are visible. In lanes 2 and 3, the *recA* scar is visible (around 400 bp). In lanes 4, 6, 7, 8, 11 and 12, two bands are visible, corresponding

to both the *recA* scar and the Kan-cassette, revealing that these colonies contained mixed populations, in which the FLP recombinase successfully excised the cassette in some cells, while unexpressed or remaining inactive in others. In lanes 5, 9 and 10, only the band corresponding to the Kan-cassette is detectable (1414 bp), demonstrating that excision did not occur in those colonies. Therefore, colonies from lanes 2 and 3 were selected for the next step. This also reveals that incubation at 37°C was sufficient to induce the FLP recombinase expression, since pCP20 is temperature-inducible.

Figure 4.5: Agarose gel obtained from colony PCR, to check for Kan-cassette elimination. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 to 6 - different colonies of MG1655 $\Delta endA::Kan^R$ + pCP20 using 2 mM of L-arabinose; 7 to 12 - different colonies of MG1655 $\Delta endA::Kan^R$ + pCP20 using 10 mM of L-arabinose. The primers *recA_check_F* and *recA_check_R* were used.

After incubation at 43°C to eliminate the helper plasmids, cells from the selected colonies were tested on three different LB agar plates to confirm plasmid curing and loss of antibiotic resistance: one without antibiotics, one supplemented with ampicillin, and one with kanamycin. Colonies in which all helper plasmids were eliminated were expected to grow only on antibiotic-free LB agar, given that both the helper plasmids and the Kan-cassette confer antibiotic resistance. Colonies on ampicillin plates indicate that pKD46 or pCP20 were not cured, while growth on kanamycin plates implies that the Kan-cassette was not removed. Four colonies from each culture selected previously were analyzed, and it was observed that only three grew solely on LB agar. To further confirm the presence of the *recA* scar, a colony PCR was performed, with two colonies from each culture that grew in antibiotic-free plates. All the tested colonies contained the *recA* scar, except for lane 5, likely because no colony was picked from the plate, since it is difficult to isolate individual colonies (Fig. 4.6). The colony from lane 6 was selected to establish cell banks of the constructed strain, MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$.

To further confirm the successful knockouts, the amplified regions with the gene scars were sequenced by Stab Vida using the same primers employed in the colony PCR. The *endA* knockout was verified with *endA_check_F* and *endA_check_R* primers, and the *recA* knockout with the corresponding *recA_check* primers. As shown in Fig. 4.7, the *recA* scar sequence includes the upstream and downstream homology regions from the original gene, one of the FRT sites and both priming sites. The second FRT site, located next to the Kan-cassette (Fig. 4.3), was likely excised during recombination,

Figure 4.6: Agarose gel obtained from colony PCR, to check for *recA* knockout. The primers *recA_check_F* and *recA_check_R* were used. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 and 3 - different colonies of MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* from colony 1; 4 and 5 - different colonies of MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* from colony 2; 6 and 7 - different colonies of MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* from colony 3.

corroborated by the fact that it is closer to the *Kan^R* gene, leaving only one FRT sequence in the genome. The sequence also contains the annealing site of the reverse primer (*recA_check_R*), and the forward primer region is not visible due to the poor quality signal at the beginning of Sanger sequencing, a common limitation of this technique, as observed in other studies [86].

The obtained scar sequences were aligned with the *E. coli* MG1655 genome from Ensembl Bacteria for both the *recA* and *endA* scars (Fig. 4.8) [82, 87]. The *recA* scar displayed nearly perfect alignment with the genomic regions immediately upstream and downstream of the *recA* gene, with only one indel at the end, typical for Sanger sequencing reads. For *endA*, the alignment was also highly conserved, showing only a single base mismatch at the beginning of the scar, which is most likely due to sequencing noise or a small variation introduced during recombination. Since this mutation does not affect the reading frame, it is not relevant or concerning.

Overall, the sequencing data corroborated the previous results, confirming the expected scars and the construction of the MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* strain. Cell banks were prepared and stored at -80°C.

Figure 4.7: Sequencing result of the PCR amplification of the *recA* scar from MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*. The primers *recA_check_F* and *recA_check_R* were used. Constructed with SnapGene.

Figure 4.8: Alignment performed with SnapGene between the *recA* and *endA* scars obtained by sequencing with the respective wild-type genes.

4.2 Shake flask cultivations

Gonçalves *et al.* (2013) have demonstrated the advantages of using the GALG20 strain for pDNA production, achieving the highest value reported for volumetric and specific pDNA yield, in both shake flask and batch bioreactor cultivations [18]. To further evaluate the effect of the *pgi* knockout on pDNA production, shake flask cultivations were performed using DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*, and GALG20, all *E. coli* strains. These experiments were carried out using different medium compositions and carbon source concentrations, as described in Section 3.2.3, with the goal of generating experimental data relevant for kinetic modeling. Additionally, pDNA production was also assessed in terms of quantity and quality.

All experiments were conducted in a batch fermentation mode, where all nutrients are provided at the time of inoculation and no further additions are made. In this project, only chemically defined media were employed, due to their high reproducibility and suitability for fermentation modeling and digital twin development. Defined media enable precise control over the concentration of each component. With minimal or defined media, it is also easier to adjust or optimize its composition, as individual components can be added to improve yields, and they usually show improved performance during scale-up [21, 45].

In batch cultures, the carbon source is usually the limiting nutrient. Although glucose is the traditional choice, its use at high concentrations is known to cause overflow metabolism, leading to acetate accumulation. Overflow metabolism occurs in aerobic conditions when high concentrations of glucose inhibit respiration (Crabtree effect) [46]. At high concentrations, acetate inhibits cell growth by lowering the extracellular and intracellular pH. Its protonated form can freely diffuse across the cell membrane and dissociate within the cytoplasm, increasing osmotic pressure and affecting the proton gradient, affecting cellular homeostasis and energy production [88]. In contrast, glycerol is often preferred as a carbon source in batch processes, as it results in high pDNA yields without overflow metabolism. It enters glycolysis downstream of the highly active phosphotransferase system (PTS), contrary to glucose, leading to a slower glycolytic flux and more balanced acetyl-CoA production compared to TCA cycle capacity

[21, 45]. In this work, both carbon sources were investigated to evaluate their effect on pDNA production.

For each medium and carbon source tested, the experimental workflow consisted of two sets of distinct experiments, as described in Section 3.2.4. The first set included time points from 0 to 9 hours and at 24 hours, and the second set included time points from 10 to 20 hours. This methodical approach was adopted to maximize data acquisition, obtaining the highest possible number of data points, to support model development, given that a larger dataset enhances the accuracy and robustness of parameter estimation.

pDNA sampling started only at 5 h, since several studies have observed that pDNA production is delayed in relation to cell growth [89]. Furthermore, for that reason, in large-scale processes in fed-batch, a two-phase strategy is often adopted: an initial biomass accumulation phase with high specific growth rates, followed by a plasmid amplification phase when the specific growth rate decreases [56]. pDNA purification was performed using 1 mL of culture instead of normalizing to the same OD, since normalization would have resulted in low plasmid concentrations and reduced accuracy.

However, collecting samples hourly was highly time-consuming, taking approximately 20–30 minutes per time point, since each experiment included twelve shake flasks (three with pDNA and three without, each in replicates). At each time point, samples were collected for OD measurements, and when required, for HPLC and pDNA quantification, and direct pH measurements from each flask were made. This sampling delay should be considered when interpreting the results, since it may result in anomalies that were not expected when comparing to uninterrupted growth in a bioreactor with automatic sampling.

Moreover, to determine the biomass concentration for comparison with other studies and calculate the specific pDNA yield, an approximate correlation factor was applied to convert $OD_{600\text{nm}}$ values to DCW. This conversion factor depends on the cultivation conditions, as the strain, growth medium and growth phase. Chemically defined media should contain fewer particles and other heterogeneous components, providing a more accurate conversion factor. For MG1655 cells grown in defined medium, Pérez-Morales *et al.* (2025) used a conversion factor of 0.37 g_{DCW}/L per $OD_{600\text{nm}}$, and Sauer *et al.* (1999) determined a factor of 0.33 [84, 85]. Therefore, an average value of 0.35 g_{DCW}/L per $OD_{600\text{nm}}$ was chosen in this work.

4.2.1 *pgi* gene knockout confirmation

In order to perform the growth experiments, it was first necessary to confirm the genotype of GALG20, ensuring that it contains the knockouts relevant for this study, which enhance pDNA production. For this purpose, a frozen WCB stored at -80°C was used to inoculate 5 mL of LB overnight. Subsequently, 5 μL of culture were used for PCR amplification, with the primers listed in Table 3.4, following the protocol described in Section 3.2.2. The agarose gel electrophoresis with the results from the PCR analysis is shown in Fig. 4.9.

In fact, since the *pgi* knockout was also generated using the λ Red recombinase system, it is pos-

sible that the selected recombinant colony, from which the cell bank was prepared, could be a mixed population, resulting from incomplete segregation, as it has been observed before in other studies [90]. Incomplete segregation may lead to a heterogenous population, where some cells carry the desired knockout but others retain the Kan-cassette, since selection is performed in the presence of kanamycin, as previously observed in the other section of this project. The other knockouts (*endA* and *recA*) were also assessed.

As a negative control, *A. succinogenes*, a wild-type bacterial strain, was also included in the PCR analysis. It carries the unmodified wild-type genes, therefore it served as a negative control for the detection of the deletion scars.

The GALG20 strain was expected to display only the gene scars left after the knockouts (*endA*: ~ 251 bp; *recA*: ~ 149 bp; *pgi*: ~ 139 bp), while *A. succinogenes* was expected to show the wild-type gene fragments (*endA*: 959 bp; *recA*: 1371 bp; *pgi*: 1414 bp). Indeed, in Fig. 4.9A, GALG20 exhibited the expected *endA* and *recA* scars (lanes 2 and 4), confirming successful knockouts. However, no amplification was detected for *pgi* (lane 6). To investigate this result, an additional PCR was performed, with two different annealing temperatures for the *pgi* primers (51°C and 55°C, corresponding to the melting temperatures of each primer, as shown in Table 3.4). The MG1655 Δ *endA* was also included to confirm the presence of the original *pgi* gene.

Figure 4.9: Agarose gels obtained from the PCR used to confirm GALG20 genotype. A: Gel to check for *endA*, *recA*, and *pgi* gene knockouts. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 - GALG20 with *endA* check primers; 3 - *A. succinogenes* with *endA* check primers; 4 - GALG20 with *recA* check primers; 5 - *A. succinogenes* with *recA* check primers; 6 - GALG20 with *pgi* check primers; 7 - *A. succinogenes* with *pgi* check primers. B: Gel to check for *pgi* gene knockout, using *pgi* check primers. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 - MG1655 Δ *endA* at $T_{\text{annealing}} = 51^{\circ}\text{C}$; 3 - GALG20 at $T_{\text{annealing}} = 51^{\circ}\text{C}$; 4 - *A. succinogenes* at $T_{\text{annealing}} = 51^{\circ}\text{C}$; 5 - MG1655 Δ *endA* at $T_{\text{annealing}} = 55^{\circ}\text{C}$; 6 - GALG20 at $T_{\text{annealing}} = 55^{\circ}\text{C}$; 7 - *A. succinogenes* at $T_{\text{annealing}} = 55^{\circ}\text{C}$.

As for the negative control, corresponding to *A. succinogenes*, the original *endA* and *pgi* genes were detected (lanes 3 and 7), while no amplification was observed for *recA*. Although this species is known to harbor the *recA* gene, the absence of amplification could be due to minor sequence differences at the primer binding sites, preventing proper annealing. The *recA* proteins are generally conserved across bacteria but might have subtle variations in their sequences, due to different evolutionary adaptation.

From Fig. 4.9B, it is evident that the GALG20 strain indeed contains the *pgi* knockout (lanes 3 and 6), displaying the scar band at a slightly higher molecular weight than expected (*pgi* scar: ~ 139 bp). This may result from the FRT regions being maintained during the recombination process. It can also be confirmed that both MG1655 Δ *endA* and *A. succinogenes* exhibit the wild-type *pgi* gene, as expected. Both annealing temperatures resulted in successful amplification, although there was more amplification with the higher annealing temperature.

These results confirm the successful knockout of *endA*, *recA* and *pgi* in the GALG20 strain, therefore validating its genotype and supporting its use in the subsequent experiments.

4.2.2 Growth experiments with Listner-based medium

To investigate the effect of the *pgi* knockout on pDNA production, growth experiments were performed using a medium based on that described by Listner *et al.* (2006). This medium had previously shown excellent scalability and high yields for several clinical grade plasmids, without causing physiological stress on *E. coli* cells. Given its proven performance, with over 1.0 g/L of pDNA achieved at pilot scale, this medium was considered an appropriate choice for use in the present work [78].

4.2.2.1 Medium optimization

The composition of the medium described by Listner *et al.* (2006), listed in Section 3.2.3, is in accordance with other typical chemically defined media used for *E. coli* cultivation, including defined sources of carbon, nitrogen, salts, and minerals. Minerals are essential for growth, metabolism, and enzymatic activity. Among them, magnesium, phosphorus, and potassium play important roles. Potassium phosphates are frequently employed, as they provide both potassium and phosphorus while also serving as buffering agents, and magnesium sulfate heptahydrate contributes with additional magnesium and sulfur, which are essential for enzymatic activity. Other essential trace elements, including molybdenum, cobalt, copper, zinc, manganese, calcium, and iron, are provided with TES, since they are required only in small amounts. Furthermore, specific components such as thiamine are included, since several engineered *E. coli* strains are auxotrophic for this vitamin [45].

The Listner-based medium was therefore employed in the experiments. However, several attempts were unsuccessful. Either the cells didn't grow in the inoculum, or, when they did, cultures in the production phase had a long lag phase or eventually stopped growing. In these attempts, at least one strain in both replicates had these behaviors, indicating that the phenomenon wasn't random (data not shown).

In the study by Listner *et al.* (2006), the production medium replaced the SSS supplement with Production Supplement Solution (PSS), with three times more thiamine-HCl. During medium and inoculum preparation, a white precipitate was persistently observed, mostly upon addition of the cells to the medium, and also when adding the TES, the SSS and the PSS. Some cultures where this precipitation occurred did not grow, particularly the DH5 α strain. In fact, DH5 α is known to be auxotrophic for

thiamine due to the *thi-1* mutation, while MG1655 is prototrophic for this vitamin [91].

The precipitation was likely due to the formation of insoluble salts from the interaction of phosphate and some divalent cations, namely magnesium or calcium [92]. To assess if this precipitation could be related to the medium composition, a precipitation test was performed, by mixing the basal medium with TES, SSS, and PSS in different combinations (data not shown). The results showed that mixing the basal medium with PSS generated slight turbidity, while adding TES led to some deposit formation. Based on the findings, SSS was selected for both the growth and production phases. After this alteration, cell growth was mostly restored, allowing the experiments to proceed. It is hypothesized that the precipitate could also contain thiamine, reducing its bioavailability. This would explain the impaired growth of DH5 α , since this strain is thiamine-auxotrophic. The other strains are thiamine prototrophs, therefore they were not affected to the same extent. To confirm this preliminary hypothesis, further analysis of the precipitate would be required. For example, lyophilization could be employed to form a powder that could be analyzed through X-ray diffraction. However, this remains a hypothesis that requires further experimental validation.

4.2.2.2 Optimization of Glucose Concentration

Since several studies have reported that high glucose concentrations can lead to growth-inhibiting concentrations of acetate in different *E. coli* strains, an experiment was performed to determine the optimal glucose concentration for this medium, using the GALG20 strain [93]. From the three strains tested, GALG20 achieved higher biomass in shake flask experiments with glucose as the carbon source, in agreement with Gonçalves *et al.* (2013) [18]. Cultivations were done at 37°C with different glucose concentrations and the time profiles for cell density and pH are shown in Fig. 4.10A,B.

By comparing the growth curves (Fig. 4.10A), it is apparent that the lowest glucose concentration tested promoted greater biomass accumulation during the exponential phase (until the 9h time point) and most of the stationary phase, reaching OD values of 5.84 and 5.13 for GALG20 harboring pDNA. However, at 24 hours, GALG20+pDNA with 10 g/L of glucose reached the highest final OD (6.44), which suggests that more substrate promoted prolonged growth and perhaps plasmid amplification. This corresponds to 2.3 g/L of biomass concentration, which is considerably low compared to other shake flasks studies, reporting concentrations of 9.6 g/L [18].

In general, across all tested glucose concentrations, cells exhibited a similar growth profile, entering the stationary phase around the 10-hour mark (Fig. 4.10A), in accordance with the growth profiles for GALG20 obtained by Lopes *et al.* (2014) [94]. However, a decrease in OD between 10 and 12 hours is observed, coinciding with the start of the second set of data points. In fact, this transient decrease might be a consequence of temporary oxygen limitation, after 10 hours of uninterrupted growth, during which the cells had become accustomed to stable conditions. During sampling, agitation was interrupted for 20 to 30 minutes per round, therefore transiently draining dissolved oxygen. This results in cell stress

Figure 4.10: Growth curves and metabolite profiles of GALG20 and GALG20+pDNA in Listner-based medium at initial glucose concentrations of 5 g/L, 10 g/L and 20 g/L for 24 h. (A) Biomass formation (log OD_{600nm}). (B) pH profiles. (C) Glucose consumption. (D) Acetate production. Closed markers represent samples from 0–9 h and 24 h. Open markers correspond to 10–20 h. At 5 g/L: GALG20 (blue) and GALG20+pDNA (orange). At 10 g/L: GALG20 (grey) and GALG20+pDNA (yellow). At 20 g/L: GALG20 (black) and GALG20+pDNA (green). Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

and eventually death of some cells, which manifests as a decrease in measured OD. Similar behavior regarding oxygen limitation has also been reported previously [95].

As for the pH profiles (Fig. 4.10B), a decrease in pH was observed for all strains except those supplemented with 5 g/L of glucose. This is in line with acetate accumulation from overflow metabolism at higher glucose concentrations, leading to acidification of the medium [12]. In the case of strains growing with 5 g/L of glucose, the low glucose concentration prevents acetate build-up, therefore the medium isn't acidified. Moreover, the GALG20+pDNA strain at 20 g/L showed the largest decrease in pH (4.84), supporting the acetate accumulation due to increased overflow metabolism in high-glucose concentrations. However, other studies report pH decreases to 6.5 under similar conditions [46].

The specific growth rate (h^{-1}) (μ) of the different strains was calculated from the exponential phase of each growth curve (Fig. 4.10A), and the results are shown in Table 4.1. At 20 g/L of glucose, the strain with pDNA exhibited the lowest growth rate ($0.122 h^{-1}$). This could be potentially explained by the overflow metabolism, resulting in acetate production, and diverting carbon away from biomass formation, therefore preventing growth. At 10 g/L of glucose, the pDNA-harboring strain achieved the highest growth

rate (0.212 h⁻¹), compared to 0.135 h⁻¹ for GALG20 without pDNA. Interestingly, apart from the 20 g/L condition, strains with pDNA displayed higher growth rates than non-transformed strains, contrary to the expected metabolic burden derived from pDNA production cited in literature. One possible explanation is that, with the *pgi* knockout, carbon flux is redirected into alternative pathways such as the PP or ED pathway, thereby increasing the production of NADPH, and ribose-5-phosphate for PP pathway. In strains harboring pDNA, these metabolites are rapidly consumed, potentially enhancing carbon uptake. As a result, glucose may be utilized more efficiently and at a faster rate, which could explain the higher biomass formation observed. In fact, *pgi*-deficient cells have been reported to experience disturbances in reducing-power balance, impairing growth [96, 97]. Under these conditions, pDNA replication can act as a sink for NADPH, and possibly ribose-5-phosphate, enabling the cell to metabolize glucose more efficiently, resulting in a higher growth rate. To support this possible mechanism, fluxomics and metabolite profiling data should be obtained.

Table 4.1: Specific growth rates (μ , h⁻¹) of GALG20 and GALG20+pDNA strains at different glucose concentrations. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

[Glucose] (g/L) Strain	Growth rate (h ⁻¹)		
	5	10	20
GALG20	0.163	0.135	0.197
GALG20 + pDNA	0.193	0.212	0.122

Profiles from glucose consumption and acetate production from HPLC (Fig. 4.10C,D) further support some of the mentioned observations. At 5 and 10 g/L, glucose was fully consumed, while at 20 g/L some glucose still remains. As for the acetate, in the 5 g/L condition, it was initially produced, but after glucose was depleted, acetate was consumed, in accordance with the absence of pH decrease (Fig. 4.10B) and with other studies [21, 95]. However, acetate continued to accumulate after glucose depletion, suggesting that possibly its production exceeded its consumption as the carbon source. At 20 g/L, the strain harboring pDNA produced 6.58 g/L of acetate, and the non-transformed strain produced 10 g/L, which is unexpected given that pDNA production typically increases acetate overflow. The explanation presented earlier, about glucose being more efficiently channelled into PP or other pathways when pDNA is produced, could also be applied. With more glucose metabolized through other pathways, less acetate will be produced. However, previous studies for GALG20 at 20 g/L of glucose reported only 1.55 g/L of acetate [18]. In another study, the pH of non-transformed cells was lower than that of pDNA-bearing cells at the 10-hour mark, possibly reflecting higher acetate accumulation, as observed in the presented data [46].

pDNA produced during these cultivations was purified and quantified, enabling the calculation of volumetric and specific pDNA yields at the different glucose concentrations (Fig. 4.11). In most time-

points, pDNA production was higher at 5 g/L (around 1.80 mg/L), in accordance with the absence of acetate accumulation and carbon uptake being used for growth and pDNA production. This is not in agreement with the fact that at 10 g/L the culture reaches the highest OD, but does not produce more pDNA, likely due to acetate accumulation. The specific yield seems to decline over time during mid- to late stationary phase, in accordance with previous findings that maximum pDNA yield is reached at mid-exponential until early stationary phase. In the late stationary phase, pDNA yield may decrease due to a decrease of plasmid copy number or degradation, in response to increased cell stress [89, 98]. A negative correlation between acetate accumulation and specific pDNA yield has also been described, in line with these results [12].

However, strong conclusions can't be drawn from this data, since the purified samples displayed sub-optimal $A_{260/280}$ and $A_{260/280}$ and lacked a defined absorbance peak at 260 nm, possibly due to low concentrations, which decreased the efficiency of the purification protocol. Compared to other studies, GALG20 at 20 g/L of glucose achieved volumetric yields of 140.8 mg/L and specific yields of 19.1 mg/g_{DCW}, contrasting with the values obtained for GALG20 in this study, of 2.32 mg/L and 2.625 mg/g_{DCW}, respectively. In fact, these values are similar to those reported for other strains, including DH5 α and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$, where pDNA yields also increase when using low-glucose concentrations [18].

Figure 4.11: Volumetric (A) and specific (B) pDNA yields of GALG20 and GALG20+pDNA in Listner-based medium at initial glucose concentrations of 5 g/L, 10 g/L and 20 g/L for 24 h. Values obtained for 5 g/L are represented in orange, at 10 g/L in yellow and at 20 g/L in green. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

To assess pDNA quality and isoform distribution, purified samples were analyzed by gel electrophoresis and then by densitometry plots, obtained with Fiji. From the 24h time point at 20 g/L of glucose, 61% of total pDNA is in the SC isoform, 14% as OC and 25% in other forms (Fig. A.5). In the linear form, pVAX1-GFP is 3697 bp in length. Conversely, at the lower glucose concentrations, the SC isoform is almost absent. The visible higher molecular weight in these lanes may correspond to plasmid multimers or gDNA contamination, although the latter is less likely since all samples were treated equally during

purification. This unexpected observation will be discussed further below, in Section 4.2.2.3. These results also contrast with published data for GALG20, in which 99.2% of pDNA was in the SC isoform [46].

Based on these results, despite the 5 g/L and 10 g/L conditions showing better results in some of the parameters mentioned, the 20 g/L glucose concentration was selected for the strain comparison growths, as this condition resulted in the highest proportion of SC pDNA, the isoform requested by regulatory authorities for therapeutic use. Additionally, this concentration was also optimized and employed in the study by Listner *et al.* (2006) in their highly productive medium [78].

It is important to note that all values reported in this study were considerably lower in comparison with previous studies. The main difference between the cultivation conditions lies on the medium composition, as the present work employed a chemically defined medium, while previous studies used complex media, with bacto-peptone and yeast extract [18]. Defined media are less nutrient-rich and possibly impose metabolic stress on cells, leading to reduced growth and production rates, as observed [99]. Furthermore, the recurrent formation of a white precipitate in these cultures, as mentioned before, could affect nutrient availability and increase metabolic stress [100].

Finally, since there were no replicates in these preliminary growths, the results are insufficient to draw firm conclusions. The main objective of this experiment was to determine the best glucose concentration to use in subsequent growths with additional strains.

4.2.2.3 Comparative Growth in Glucose-Based Medium

To evaluate the effect of the *pgi* knockout on pDNA production, shake flask cultivations were performed using three *E. coli* strains, DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*, and GALG20, with Listner-based medium containing 20 g/L of glucose. Interestingly, the non-transformed DH5 α only displayed normal growth behavior when using a cell bank derived from glycerol-based medium. This may be due to the fact that it contained less precipitate than the glucose medium, which likely increased nutrient availability, including thiamine, therefore promoting growth. A growth control of DH5 α in LB medium was performed and proceeded as expected, without cell death, confirming that the issue was associated with the composition of the Listner-based medium.

The growth profiles of the strains showed some differences (Fig. 4.12A), with the second set of time-points (10h to 20h) not being quite complementary to the first. This discrepancy is likely attributed to sampling limitations, since, as mentioned, each time point's sampling required around 25 min. Therefore, the 9h of growth effectively corresponded to slightly more than half that. In contrast, in the second set, cells were able to grow uninterrupted for 10h. Additionally, the starting volume of the second set and the ending volume of the first set differed significantly due to sampling, which can influence oxygen availability and affect culture behavior. Moreover, the non-transformed MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* strain seemed to display a long lag phase, which is in accordance with the *recA* knockout that was

performed. Indeed, other literature reports showed that deletion of a *recA* homolog in bacteria can result in a markedly prolonged lag phase [101]. In general, gene knockouts can disrupt metabolic or regulatory pathways, requiring cells to adapt before entering exponential growth. This likely explains the lag phase observed (Fig. 4.12A) [102]. Although both this strain and GALG20 carry the *recA* knockout, GALG20 had undergone multiple passages and was maintained as a stable cell bank, likely giving it more time to adapt to the mutation and culture conditions. In contrast, MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* had only recently been engineered, which may have contributed to its slower initial growth. Regarding pH profiles (Fig. 4.12B), a general decrease is observed, and it stabilizes in the stationary phase, as expected, since glucose depletion possibly halts overflow metabolism and acetate production. Maximum biomass obtained for pDNA-harboring DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* and GALG20 strains were 1.66 ± 0.1 g/L, 1.27 ± 0.3 g/L and 1.71 ± 0.1 g/L, respectively, contrasting with previous studies, reporting 3.8 ± 0.2 g/L, 3.5 ± 0.3 g/L and 10.9 ± 0.2 g/L, respectively, although in both cases GALG20 exhibited the highest biomass [18].

Figure 4.12: Growth curves and metabolite profiles of DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* and GALG20 in Listner glucose-based medium for 24 h. (A) Biomass formation (log OD_{600nm}). (B) pH profiles. (C) Glucose consumption. (D) Acetate production. DH5 α (blue), MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (orange), GALG20 (grey), DH5 α +pDNA (yellow), MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*+pDNA (black) and GALG20+pDNA (green). Closed markers represent samples from 0–9 h and 24 h. Open markers correspond to 10–20 h. For visualization purposes, MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* is represented as MG1655 in the legend. The mean results of two replicates ($n=2$) for each strain are presented, along with standard deviation error bars. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

The μ of the different strains was calculated (Table 4.2), using the log plot (Fig. 4.12A). DH5 α +pDNA exhibited a significantly lower rate (0.081 ± 0.0021 h⁻¹) in comparison to the non-transformed strain

($0.102 \pm 0.0014 \text{ h}^{-1}$). This result is in line with the metabolic burden imposed by pDNA production, which redirected resources away from growth. The rate of MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ ($0.088 \pm 0.0046 \text{ h}^{-1}$) was significantly lower than those of both DH5 α ($0.102 \pm 0.0014 \text{ h}^{-1}$) and GALG20 ($0.110 \pm 0.0050 \text{ h}^{-1}$), attributable to the longer lag phase displayed (Fig. 4.12A). For pDNA-harboring strains, the rates of DH5 α ($0.081 \pm 0.0021 \text{ h}^{-1}$) and MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ ($0.080 \pm 0.0055 \text{ h}^{-1}$) were both significantly lower than that of GALG20 ($0.100 \pm 0.0005 \text{ h}^{-1}$). This is also in accordance with the *pgi* knockout, which is proposed to enable a more efficient use of glucose by redirecting the flux to other pathways. However, these rates were considerably lower than those reported previously under the same conditions [18].

Table 4.2: Specific growth rates (μ , h^{-1}) of DH5 α , MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ and GALG20, with and without pDNA, in Listner glucose-based medium. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm. Values are presented as mean \pm SD.

Strain	Growth rate (h^{-1})	
	Non-transformed	pDNA-harboring
DH5 α	0.102 ± 0.0014	0.081 ± 0.0021
MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$	0.088 ± 0.0046	0.080 ± 0.0055
GALG20	0.110 ± 0.0050	0.100 ± 0.0005

Regarding glucose consumption and glycerol production (Fig. 4.12C, D), sampling limitations are also visible. At the 24-h mark glucose hasn't been totally consumed, while in the second set it appears fully consumed. The transformed GALG20 strain displays a higher glucose consumption rate accompanied by a higher acetate concentration at 24 h ($4.78 \pm 0.50 \text{ g/L}$), contradicting what would be expected from the *pgi* knockout. It would be expected for the carbon flux to be redirected into the PP pathway and a reduction in acetate overflow, which is not observed. Possibly carbon flux could have been redirected into another route, such as the ED pathway, which typically accounts for only a minor portion of glucose catabolism [18]. In fact, under nutrient-limiting conditions, a global metabolic shift has been reported in other bacteria, where cells switch from catabolic pathways into alternative routes when using glucose as the carbon source. Several ED enzymes, including glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (Zwf), gluconokinase, and KDPG/KHG aldolase (highlighted in Fig. 4.13) have been shown to be up-regulated under these conditions. The yield of glucose via this pathway is 2 molecules of pyruvate (the same as in glycolysis), 1 mol of NADPH, 1 mol of NADH and 1 mol of ATP. From the pyruvate, acetate formation is highly likely, as in glycolysis, which could explain acetate production despite the *pgi* knockout. The conditions in the studied system, as precipitate formation and a nutrient-poor defined medium, may have imposed nutrient limitation, resulting in this shift [103]. The value of initial glucose detected in Fig. 4.12 (around 13.40 g/L instead of 20 g/L) further supports possible problems with nutrient availability. Additionally, earlier reports indicate that for MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ the acetate concentration was $5.74 \pm 0.04 \text{ g/L}$, for DH5 α $4.72 \pm 0.04 \text{ g/L}$ and for GALG20 $1.55 \pm 0.02 \text{ g/L}$, while in the current study the values ($2.16 \pm 0.01 \text{ g/L}$ for DH5 α and $1.93 \pm 0.15 \text{ g/L}$ for MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$) are lower (except

for GALG20) [18].

Figure 4.13: Overview of central carbon metabolism showing major routes (glycolysis, ED, PP pathways and TCA cycle). The *pgi* knockout is highlighted in red, and enzymes found to be up-regulated under nutrient-limiting conditions are indicated in purple. Purple arrows indicate the resulting shifts in carbon flux. Adapted from [104].

The pDNA volumetric and specific yields were calculated for all strains (Fig. 4.14A, B). The highest volumetric yield was obtained by GALG20 at 12h and MG1655Δ*endA*Δ*recA* at 24h (2.18 ± 0.62 mg/L and 2.18 ± 1.46 mg/L, respectively), while DH5α achieved 1.76 ± 0.37 mg/L. These results are considerably lower than those reported for GALG20 (140.8 ± 0.8 mg/L) but are similar to literature values for DH5α and MG1655Δ*endA*Δ*recA* (1.3 ± 0.1 mg/L and 1.5 ± 0.1 mg/L, respectively). This suggests that the *pgi* knockout did not result in the expected increase of pDNA production, in accordance with the theory of redirection of carbon flux for alternative pathways which do not produce nucleotide precursors nor reduce acetate production, instead of PP pathway, due to restricted nutrient availability. Such trend was also observed for the specific yield, with GALG20 reaching 1.38 ± 0.13 mg/g DCW, DH5α 1.354 ± 0.14 mg/g_{DCW} and MG1655Δ*endA*Δ*recA* 1.839 ± 0.42 mg/g_{DCW}. These results are slightly higher for DH5α and MG1655Δ*endA*Δ*recA* compared to reported values (0.8 ± 0.1 mg/g_{DCW}) but substantially lower for GALG20 (19.1 ± 1.5 mg/g_{DCW}) [18]. There were no statistically significant differences between the three

strains.

Through densitometry analysis of gel electrophoresis (Fig. A.6), the isoform distributions were obtained for each strain over time (Fig. 4.14C, D, E). Interestingly, GALG20 presents almost no SC plasmid fraction, while MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* shows SC at earlier time-points and DH5 α mostly retains SC throughout the entire growth. The high-molecular-weight band observed in the gels is hypothesized to represent plasmid multimers, corresponding to higher-order structures arising from errant segregation during replication [64].

Figure 4.14: Volumetric (A) and specific (B) pDNA yields and isoform distribution (C, D, E) of DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* and GALG20 in Listner glucose-based medium for 12h, 15h, 18h and 24h. In A and B: DH5 α (orange), MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (yellow), GALG20 (green). In C, D, and E: multimers (pink), OC (purple), linear (dark blue), SC (light blue). For visualization purposes, MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* is represented as MG1655 in the legend. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm. The mean results of two replicates (n=2) for each strain are presented, along with standard deviation error bars, when possible. OC - open circular. SC - supercoiled.

Over time, these multimers appear to accumulate and increase in number of repeats per molecule, known as dimer catastrophe [64]. An increase in the multimers fraction is visible over time (4.14C, D, E). Moreover, multimer formation is known to promote plasmid instability and eventually loss, which is in agreement with the decline in yield observed for GALG20 after the 12-hour mark [65].

Multimer formation can be influenced by plasmid-encoded, chromosomal and environmental factors. The plasmid under study (pVAX1-GFP) has a high-copy number pMB1 origin, which belongs to the ColE1 family of plasmid origins. In fact, ColE1-type origins have been shown to multimerize more

readily when compared to low- or medium- copy plasmids [64]. Regarding the chromosomal factors, all three strains are *recA*-deficient, inactivating the major RecBCD homologous recombination pathway. However, *recA*-independent recombination mechanisms have also been reported. For instance, a study with a *rarA* deletion (encoding for RarA recombinase) in *recA*-deficient strains showed a significantly decreased recombination rate by a factor of 11- and 6-fold at 104 bp and 411 bp homology sharing regions plasmids, respectively. In fact, *rarA* presents extensive homology between different species, suggesting a conserved function in DNA metabolism [105]. Perhaps, in the present system, this protein contributes to the multimer fraction observed for both in MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* and GALG20, despite the *recA* knockout.

Moreover, environmental stresses may exacerbate multimerization. For instance, De la Cruz *et al.* (2024) conducted a study with the similar goal of increasing the PP flux, by *zwf* overexpression, *pykA* deletion or substitution of the PTS by galactose permease. It was also reported plasmid multimerization in *recA*-deficient strains, which was attributed as a result of stress conditions, caused by gene overexpression and/or for using two carbon sources [106]. Likewise, in the present study, sources of cellular stress, such as sub-optimal medium and low nutrient availability due to precipitation, may drive multimer formation. Also, specifically for GALG20, the redirection of carbon flux possibly to the ED pathway, under nutrient-poor conditions, may perturb redox balance (related to NADPH/NADH ratios), therefore causing oxidative stress leading to strand breaks, which may affect replication or repair mechanisms, such as homologous recombination [107]. Moreover, the PP pathway produces 2 NADPH per glucose, while the ED pathway nets 1 NADPH per glucose [108]. Since NADPH is crucial for reductive biosynthesis and maintaining redox balance and mitigating oxidative stress, favoring the ED pathway may potentially increase the oxidative stress burden compared with flux through the PP pathway [109]. This could be a possible explanation for increased multimerization for GALG20, compared to MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*.

Additionally, cells normally have multimer-resolution systems, resulting in single monomers before cell division. For example, the Xer-mediated dimer resolution site *mwr* on plasmid pJHCMW1 has been shown to display strong osmoregulation: under high-osmolarity conditions, the mechanism is inefficient, while under low-osmolarity medium it is efficient. Thus, since Listner medium possibly has relatively high osmolarity due to salts, this multimer-resolution system might be down-regulated, contributing to the accumulation of multimers [65]. De la Cruz *et al.* (2024) also speculate a possible link of increased multimerization to the inhibition of site-specific recombinases [106].

As for DH5 α , the *gyrA96* mutation results in higher activity of DNA gyrase that introduces negative supercoiling, which could possibly explain the higher SC content in this strain.

Overall, the exact reasons for elevated multimerization remain unclear. The presented mechanisms might be plausible but speculative, and need to be experimentally validated.

4.2.2.4 Optimization of Glycerol Concentration

Glycerol has frequently been used as an alternative carbon source to glucose given that it results in lower levels of acetate accumulation. Indeed, glycerol is metabolized via phosphorylation to glycerol-3-phosphate by glycerol kinase, and then oxidized to dihydroxyacetone phosphate, which enters glycolysis. Since it bypasses the early steps of glycolysis that generate ATP, it is considered a low-energy substrate. Accordingly, considering that glycerol uptake is slower and limited by prior reactions, the cells can complete full carbon oxidation via the TCA cycle instead of diverting it to acetate production, avoiding overflow metabolism [110]. Moreover, the use of glycerol as a carbon source has been associated with higher pDNA yields. However, high glycerol concentrations can also lead to high acetate production [21]. Therefore, growth experiments were conducted to determine the optimal glycerol concentration in this medium, using the DH5 α strain, which achieved higher biomass in shake flask experiments. The experiments were performed at 37°C with different glycerol concentrations, and the time profiles for cell density, metabolite consumption/formation and pH are shown in Fig. 4.15.

Figure 4.15: Growth curves and metabolite profiles of DH5 α and DH5 α +pDNA in Listner-based medium at initial glycerol concentrations of 5 g/L, 10 g/L and 20 g/L for 24 h. (A) Biomass formation (log OD_{600nm}). (B) pH profiles. (C) Glycerol consumption. (D) Acetate production. Closed markers represent samples from 0–9 h and 24 h. Open markers correspond to 10–20 h. At 5 g/L: DH5 α (blue) and DH5 α +pDNA (orange). At 10 g/L: DH5 α (grey) and DH5 α +pDNA (yellow). At 20 g/L: DH5 α (black) and DH5 α +pDNA (green). Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

By analyzing the growth curves (Fig. 4.15A), the highest biomass for DH5 α was observed for the

20 g/L glycerol condition at most time-points, with pDNA. However, at 24h, the 10 g/L culture, also with pDNA reached an OD of 7.88 (biomass of 2.7 g/L), suggesting that the high glycerol concentration (20 g/L) might have inhibited growth. Still, the biomass value was lower than previously reported values of 11.3 g/L for 20 g/L of glycerol [18].

All strains exhibited a similar growth profile, with a slight decrease in the second set of time points, as observed before and possibly attributable to temporary oxygen limitation. Interestingly, none of the cultures reached the stationary phase over 24h (Fig. 4.15A), contrary to the growth profile reported by Lopes *et al.* (2014) [21].

The μ of the different strains was calculated with different initial glycerol concentrations (Table 4.3), using the log plot (Fig. 4.15A). The highest μ was observed at 5 g/L with pDNA (0.125 h⁻¹), and the lowest at 5 g/L without pDNA (0.085 h⁻¹). Notably, in the non-transformed cells, the effect of glycerol concentration on μ is directly proportional, while in the pDNA-bearing cells, the effect is inversely proportional. A possible explanation is that higher glycerol concentrations may result in overflow metabolism and acetate accumulation associated to plasmid metabolic burden, which can inhibit growth. Although other studies have reported higher growth rates (0.27 h⁻¹) at 5 g/L [21], some studies also confirmed that higher glycerol concentrations led to lower μ , corroborating this data [78].

Table 4.3: Specific growth rates (μ , h⁻¹) of DH5 α and DH5 α +pDNA strains at different glycerol concentrations. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

[Glycerol] (g/L) Strain	Growth rate (h ⁻¹)		
	5	10	20
DH5 α	0.085	0.105	0.108
DH5 α + pDNA	0.125	0.111	0.109

As for the pH profiles (Fig. 4.15B), pDNA-bearing cells at 20 g/L exhibit the highest pH decline (5.52) after 24h, in accordance with overflow metabolism-driven acetate production. For most time points, pDNA-bearing cells exhibit lower pH than non-transformed cells, possibly due to increased metabolic burden and higher acetate accumulation caused by pDNA production.

The profiles of glycerol consumption and acetate production from HPLC (Fig. 4.15C,D) support these observations. Glycerol was not fully consumed until the last time point, which coincides with the cultures remaining in the exponential phase, as observed (Fig. 4.15A). However, at the 24-hour time point, at 20 g/L, glycerol had not been consumed. Accordingly, acetate production was significant only at this glycerol concentration at 24h. Indeed, the pDNA-bearing strain produced 5.42 g/L of acetate, while the non-transformed strain produced only 3.22 g/L. This discrepancy also matches the differences observed in the pH profiles, with a lower pH when pDNA is produced. Increased acetate production also inhibits growth, as evidenced by the lowest growth rate observed in the pDNA-producing strain at 20 g/L of

glycerol. Other studies have reported similar acetate production levels: 4.8 g/L at 5 g/L of glycerol and around 5 g/L of acetate at 6 g/L of glycerol [21, 94].

In the case of DH5 α , this strain lacks the *pgi* mutation and therefore no mechanism exists to redirect carbon flux and avoid overflow metabolism. Cells are able to sense low carbon levels, activating the carbon stress response, inducing *rpoS* transcription and other genes involved in carbon scavenging and acetate recycling [110]. The factor RpoS is a master regulator of the general stress response. In fact, under conditions of high acetate generation from glycerol metabolism, elevated expression of RpoS has been reported, confirming that acetate accumulation and glycerol utilization can activate cellular stress responses [111].

pDNA was purified and quantified, for determination of volumetric and specific pDNA yields at different glycerol concentrations (Fig. 4.16). In general, pDNA production peaked at 10 g/L of glycerol (3.19 mg/L) and was lowest for 20 g/L, particularly at later time points. This observation is in line with the absence of acetate accumulation in the 10 g/L condition, contrary to the 20 g/L condition. Since acetate production diverts carbon from biosynthesis mechanisms, including pDNA synthesis, this could explain the lower levels of pDNA at 20 g/L of glycerol. Regarding the specific yield, a drastic decline is observed over time, with the highest value obtained at 5 g/L (7.5 mg/g_{DCW}). In comparison, Gonçalves *et al.* (2013) reported a specific yield of 4.4 mg/g_{DCW}, but a higher volumetric yield of 34.7 mg/L [18]. Moreover, a similar decline over time, by more than half, was reported in other studies using glycerol [112].

Figure 4.16: Volumetric (A) and specific (B) pDNA yields of DH5 α and DH5 α +pDNA in Listner-based medium at initial glycerol concentrations of 5 g/L, 10 g/L and 20 g/L for 24 h. Values obtained for 5 g/L are represented in orange, at 10 g/L in yellow and at 20 g/L in green. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

pDNA quality and isoform distribution were determined after purification and gel electrophoresis. At 24h (Fig. A.7), cells growing at 5 g/L and 10 g/L of glycerol contained 41,6 % and 43,6 % of SC isoform, respectively, while at 20 g/L cells produced 64,2 % of SC pDNA. Other isoforms are also observed, such as multimers, OC, and linear (in order from the top of the gel).

After analyzing all the information, a glycerol concentration of 10 g/L was selected, since it exhibited less acetate accumulation, while yielding higher biomass and pDNA yield. This concentration was also employed in the study by Listner *et al.* (2006) in their highly productive medium [78].

It is important to note that this experiment was also intended to identify the optimal concentration of glycerol. The drawn conclusions should not be considered definitive since there were no replicates in the experiment. Additionally, there may be errors in the pDNA measurements, as the purification indicators were outside the expected ranges.

4.2.2.5 Comparative Growth in Glycerol-Based Medium

To assess whether glycerol as a carbon source enhances pDNA yield compared to glucose and its effect on the *pgi* knockout, shake flask cultivations were performed for the three strains in Listner-based medium containing 10 g/L glycerol.

The two sets of growth profiles appeared complementary, with differences among strains (Fig. 4.17A). Both non-transformed MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* and GALG20 showed an extended lag phase, likely due to their engineered background with knockouts and the lower energy yield of glycerol, possibly requiring longer adaptation. As for the pH profiles (Fig. 4.17B), a general decrease was observed during the second set, coinciding with higher biomass (Fig. 4.17A) and in line with acetate accumulation (Fig. 4.17D). DH5 α showed the highest acetate production (1.61 ± 0.11 g/L) and the lowest pH (5.57 ± 0.042), though not significantly different from the other strains. Maximum biomass obtained for pDNA-harboring DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* and GALG20 strains were 2.81 ± 0.45 g/L, 2.85 ± 0.15 g/L and 2.70 ± 0.10 g/L, respectively, contrasting with previous studies, reporting 11.3 ± 0.9 g/L, 7.7 ± 0.8 g/L and 8.5 ± 0.5 g/L, although in those studies 20 g/L of glycerol were used instead of 10 g/L [18]. Regarding glucose consumption and glycerol production (Fig. 4.17C, D), sampling limitations are also visible, with some increases of glycerol instead of consumption. Compared with literature values, acetate production was higher for DH5 α (1.61 ± 0.11 g/L vs 0.05 ± 0.01 g/L) and GALG20 (1.24 ± 0.10 g/L vs 0.61 ± 0.04 g/L), but lower for MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (0.18 ± 0.02 g/L vs 3.86 ± 0.01 g/L) [18].

The μ of the different strains was calculated (Table 4.4), using the log plot (Fig. 4.17A), and non-transformed DH5 α (0.111 ± 0.011 h⁻¹) and MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (0.110 ± 0.003 h⁻¹) showed significantly higher rates than GALG20 (0.054 ± 0.004 h⁻¹), likely because the *pgi* knockout in GALG20 slows glycerol metabolism by blocking glycolysis, which is already a less efficiently metabolized carbon source. Moreover, non-transformed GALG20 displayed a significantly lower rate than its pDNA-harboring strain (0.114 ± 0.0001 h⁻¹), which is counterintuitive. Perhaps, pDNA production may shift the equilibrium and allow for more glycerol uptake and consumption, as observed in Fig. 4.17C, leading to a higher growth rate. Still, these rates were considerably lower than those reported previously under 20 g/L of glycerol (DH5 α , 0.55 ± 0.01 h⁻¹; MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*, 0.60 ± 0.01 h⁻¹; GALG20, 0.60 ± 0.05 h⁻¹) [18].

As observed in Fig. 4.18, the volumetric pDNA yield increases over time, in accordance with the

Figure 4.17: Growth curves and metabolite profiles of *DH5 α* , *MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA* and *GALG20* in Listner glycerol-based medium for 24 h. (A) Biomass formation ($\log OD_{600nm}$). (B) pH profiles. (C) Glycerol consumption. (D) Acetate production. *DH5 α* (blue), *MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA* (orange), *GALG20* (grey), *DH5 α +pDNA* (yellow), *MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA+pDNA* (black) and *GALG20+pDNA* (green). Closed markers represent samples from 0–9 h and 24 h. Open markers correspond to 10–20 h. For visualization purposes, *MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA* is represented as *MG1655* in the legend. The mean results of two replicates ($n=2$) for each strain is presented, along with standard deviation error bars. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

cultures remaining in exponential growth. The specific yield decreases over time, as reported before in glycerol-based growths [112]. *MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA* showed a significantly higher specific yield than both *DH5 α* and *GALG20*, in accordance with previous studies [18]. Compared with literature values, for volumetric yields, all strains exhibited lower values: *DH5 α* , 10.77 ± 0.33 mg/L vs. 34.7 ± 0.6 mg/L; *MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA*, 11.44 ± 2.04 mg/L vs. 79.3 ± 1.4 mg/L; *GALG20*, 9.90 ± 0.81 mg/L vs. 65.5 ± 1.4 mg/L, but with *GALG20* producing slightly less than *MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA* in both cases. For specific yields, *DH5 α* showed values comparable to those in the literature (5.24 ± 0.07 mg/g_{DCW} vs. 4.4 ± 0.3 mg/g_{DCW}), while for *MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA* and *GALG20* these were lower (8.80 ± 0.48 mg/g_{DCW} vs 11.5 ± 0.8 mg/g_{DCW}; 5.42 ± 0.01 mg/g_{DCW} vs 19.1 ± 1.5 mg/g_{DCW}, respectively). [18] Regarding isoform distribution, obtained by densitometry analysis (Fig. A.8), both *DH5 α* and *GALG20* produced a high proportion of the SC isoform, mostly meeting the FDA requirement of at least 80% [27]. In contrast, *MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA* showed a higher proportion of multimeric forms. This may be attributed to heightened physiological stress, requiring additional time to adapt to glycerol, a relatively low-energy carbon source, as a newly constructed knockout strain, which could promote multimeriza-

Table 4.4: Specific growth rates (μ , h^{-1}) of DH5 α , MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ and GALG20, with and without pDNA, in Listner glycerol-based medium. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm. Values are presented as mean \pm SD.

Strain	Growth rate (h^{-1})	
	Non-transformed	pDNA-harboring
DH5 α	0.111 \pm 0.011	0.090 \pm 0.008
MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$	0.110 \pm 0.003	0.105 \pm 0.002
GALG20	0.054 \pm 0.004	0.114 \pm 0.0001

tion. Also, the use of the Listner medium, with slight precipitation, may have caused additional stress, explaining the generally lower values compared to the literature.

GALG20 did not show any evident benefit from the *pgi* knockout when grown on glycerol, since overflow metabolism does not occur with this carbon source, also reflected in the reduced acetate production. Glycerol metabolism involves additional enzymatic steps that, in a wild-type strain, prevent excessive carbon flux through glycolysis. As a low-energy carbon source, redirecting flux through the other pathways provides little additional energy, restricting growth and pDNA production [110, 113].

Figure 4.18: Volumetric (A) and specific (B) pDNA yields and isoform distribution (C, D, E) of DH5 α , MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ and GALG20 in Listner glycerol-based medium for 12h, 15h, 18h and 24h. In A and B: DH5 α (orange), MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ (yellow), GALG20 (green). In C, D, and E: multimers (pink), OC (purple), SC (light blue). For visualization purposes, MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$ is represented as MG1655 in the legend. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm. The mean results of two replicates (n=2) for each strain are presented, along with standard deviation error bars, when possible. OC - open circular. SC - supercoiled.

4.2.3 Growth experiments with Wang medium

Another strategy to increase pDNA yield, beyond strain engineering, is medium optimization via amino acid limitation or starvation. Ideally, this is triggered in strains carrying mutations in stringent-response genes, but it can also be effective in non-mutant cells. For example, a low tryptone concentration, which translates to a limited amino-acid supply, yielded a high specific pDNA yield [114].

Instead of following conventional medium optimization, which is based on trial-and-error and labor-intensive, time-consuming work, an alternative is to use a stoichiometric medium design approach. Wang *et al.* (2001) followed this method, based on the assumption that each nutrient's stoichiometric coefficient is derived based on its role in biomass formation and product synthesis (Fig. A.9). Specifically for plasmid amplification, abundant nucleotide pools and extra energy must be available, while other cellular activities should be minimised. Therefore, amino-acid limitation slows cellular protein synthesis and cell growth, which reduces competition for carbon and energy and provides a larger window for plasmid replication prior to cell division [2].

In their study, Wang *et al.* (2001) developed a defined medium using glucose and salts, supplemented with amino acids. Glutamine, aspartate and glycine are consumed for the synthesis of RNA, DNA and pDNA. Depending on the plasmid replicon, different amino acids should be selected, since other amino acids might decrease pDNA stability. One amino acid from each family pool was chosen, avoiding the ones that affect stability. Therefore, the mixture of six amino acids consisted of glycine, leucine, histidine, aspartate, glutamine and tryptophan. The optimized medium composition is listed on Section 3.2.3.

4.2.3.1 Comparative Growth in Wang-Based Medium

To evaluate the effect of amino acid limitation on pDNA yield and its potential influence on the *pgi* knockout, shake flask cultivations were performed for the three strains in Wang-based medium containing 10 g/L of glucose.

Overall, the two sets of growth profiles do not seem complementary, since the second set appears to lag behind the first (Fig. 4.19A,B). This may be attributed to the fact that in the second set the inoculum was grown for one day instead of overnight. In falcon tubes, the oxygen availability is limited, so a longer inoculum time may have led to increased cell death or physiological stress. When this inoculum was transferred to fresh medium, the cells displayed a longer lag period for adaptation [115].

The μ of the different strains was also calculated (Table 4.5). Analyzing both sets of data, the cultures appeared to remain in the exponential phase, which is favorable for pDNA production. Growth among all strains, with and without pDNA, showed no significant differences, reaching similar maximum biomass concentrations and μ values. For the pDNA-harboring strains, the maximum biomass concentrations were 1.25 ± 0.06 g/L for DH5 α , 0.91 ± 0.05 g/L for MG1655 $\Delta endA\Delta recA$, and 1.11 ± 0.05 g/L for GALG20. For these, the corresponding μ values were 0.099 ± 0.025 h⁻¹, 0.084 ± 0.012 h⁻¹ and

Figure 4.19: Growth curves and metabolite profiles of DH5 α , MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA and GALG20 in Wang-based medium for 24 h. (A) Biomass formation (log OD_{600nm}). (B) pH profiles. (C) Glucose consumption. (D) Acetate production. DH5 α (blue), MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (orange), GALG20 (grey), DH5 α +pDNA (yellow), MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA+pDNA (black) and GALG20+pDNA (green). Closed markers represent samples from 0–9 h and 24 h. Open markers correspond to 10–20 h. For visualization purposes, MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA is represented as MG1655 in the legend. The mean results of two replicates ($n=2$) for each strain are presented, along with standard deviation error bars. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

$0.063 \pm 0.012 \text{ h}^{-1}$, respectively. These values were notably lower than those previously obtained in this work for glucose or reported in the literature for other media, in line with a reduced allocation of cellular resources to growth, as evidenced by the lower glucose consumption rate (Fig. 4.19C). However, Wang *et al.* (2001) reported higher values with this medium: $4.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ g/L}$ for biomass, 0.41 h^{-1} and 0.47 h^{-1} for the untransformed and transformed JM109 strains, respectively, in accordance with the modest difference also observed between these two cultures in the present work [2].

The pH (Fig. 4.19B) decreased slightly throughout the cultivation but remained relatively stable overall. Despite the high acetate concentrations observed (Fig. 4.19D), the limited pH variation suggests that the medium possesses good buffering capacity. Given the low growth rates, overflow metabolism should be minimal, which contradicts the high acetate production. Perhaps, the apparent high acetate levels may not fully reflect true acetate accumulation, as amino acid limitation could have induced the production of other metabolites co-eluting with acetate, leading to overestimated and some irregular values. A similar inconsistency was noted for glucose measurements. Notably, GALG20 exhibited the lowest acetate concentration at the 24-hour mark ($8.02 \pm 0.33 \text{ g/L}$, higher than previous reports also

using glucose), suggesting that the *pgi* knockout may partially redirect carbon flux through the PP pathway, although some carbon might still be diverted to the ED pathway, leading to acetate accumulation [18].

Table 4.5: Specific growth rates (μ , h^{-1}) of DH5 α , MG1655 $\Delta\text{endA}\Delta\text{recA}$ and GALG20, with and without pDNA, in Wang-based medium. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm. Values are presented as mean \pm SD.

Strain	Growth rate (h^{-1})	
	Non-transformed	pDNA-harboring
DH5 α	0.077 \pm 0.027	0.099 \pm 0.025
MG1655 $\Delta\text{endA}\Delta\text{recA}$	0.081 \pm 0.004	0.084 \pm 0.012
GALG20	0.071 \pm 0.004	0.063 \pm 0.012

As shown in Fig. 4.20, the volumetric pDNA yield increased over time, in line with the cultures remaining in exponential growth. The specific yield remained relatively constant over time, which is desirable for stable production performance and creating a wider window of opportunity for harvest [114]. From the three strains tested, DH5 α exhibited the highest specific yield (11.37 \pm 0.62 mg/g_{DCW}), significantly higher than MG1655 $\Delta\text{endA}\Delta\text{recA}$ and GALG20 (3.45 \pm 0.36 mg/g_{DCW} and 3.56 \pm 0.09 mg/g_{DCW}, respectively), and higher than the values previously reported using glucose (1.8 \pm 0.7 mg/g_{DCW}). This is in agreement with previous reports, where using this medium led to increased specific yield in comparison to other media [2]. Importantly, DH5 α carries the *relA1* mutation. RelA encodes the enzyme ppGpp synthetase I, which catalyzes the synthesis of the alarmone guanosine-5-diphosphate-3-diphosphate (ppGpp) during amino acid starvation in *E. coli*. This is known as the stringent response, which normally suppresses plasmid replication. Hence, the *relA1* mutation avoids the synthesis of ppGpp during amino acid starvation or nutrient limitation, resulting in a relaxed response, increasing plasmid amplification [39]. This would explain the increased specific pDNA yield observed for Dh5 α .

However, the volumetric yields obtained here were considerably lower than those reported by Wang *et al.* (2001) (30 \pm 2 mg/L). All the lower values and rates observed, in comparison to that study, might be related to strain and plasmid differences, given that their study used the JM109 strain with the pcDNA3S plasmid, but mostly due to differences in cultivation conditions, since their experiments were conducted in a 2 L bioreactor. Bioreactors enable precise control of pH and dissolved oxygen at defined set points, while shake flasks do not, hindering optimal growth over a long culture period [2, 95].

Concerning isoform distribution (Fig. 4.20C, D, E), determined through gel densitometry (Fig. A.10), all strains exhibited a high proportion of the SC isoform, meeting the FDA requirement of at least 80% at all time points, except DH5 α at 24h [27]. In fact, a similar observation was reported by Dorward *et al.* (2019) when inducing amino acid starvation, where the SC fraction increased to 90%, attributed to changes in intracellular ATP/ADP ratios. These were associated with shifting environmental conditions, which have been reported to promote supercoiling [114].

However, for GALG20, no apparent benefit of the *pgi* knockout was observed, which is unexpected given that glucose was used as the carbon source. One possible explanation is that amino acid limitation activated the stringent response, altering the transcription of genes that redirect metabolism, or creating other stress conditions that upregulate alternative pathways, such as the ED pathway, known to be activated under nutrient-limiting conditions, diverting flux from the PP pathway [15, 103]. This explanation would also concur with the acetate accumulation and the lack of improvement in pDNA yield.

Figure 4.20: Volumetric (A) and specific (B) pDNA yields and isoform distribution (C, D, E) of DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* and GALG20 in Wang-based medium for 12h, 15h, 18h and 24h. In A and B: DH5 α (orange), MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (yellow), GALG20 (green). In C, D, and E: multimers (pink), OC (purple), linear (dark blue), SC (light blue). For visualization purposes, MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* is represented as MG1655 in the legend. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm. The mean results of two replicates (n=2) for each strain are presented, along with standard deviation error bars, when possible. OC - open circular. SC - supercoiled.

4.2.4 Comparison of Growth-Associated Parameters and pDNA Yields in Different Media

After analyzing each growth experiment, a comparative assessment of the different media composition and their impact on growth-associated parameters and pDNA yields was performed. Table 4.6 summarizes all calculated parameters for the three media in the DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA*, and GALG20 strains.

In general, concerning experimental observations, the Listner glucose-based medium exhibited con-

Table 4.6: Comparison of growth and pDNA production parameters of DH5 α , MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA, and GALG20 under different carbon and nutrient sources. Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

Parameter/value	DH5 α	MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA	GALG20
μ (h ⁻¹)			
Glucose	0.081 \pm 0.002	0.080 \pm 0.076	0.100 \pm 0.000
Glycerol	0.090 \pm 0.008	0.105 \pm 0.002	0.114 \pm 0.000
Glucose + amino acids	0.099 \pm 0.025	0.084 \pm 0.012	0.063 \pm 0.012
Maximum biomass (g/L)			
Glucose	1.657 \pm 0.134	1.267 \pm 0.297	1.708 \pm 0.085
Glycerol	2.805 \pm 0.445	2.847 \pm 0.148	2.699 \pm 0.099
Glucose + amino acids	1.246 \pm 0.057	0.908 \pm 0.049	1.111 \pm 0.049
Maximum acetate (g/L)			
Glucose	2.156 \pm 0.010	1.932 \pm 0.151	4.781 \pm 0.499
Glycerol	1.606 \pm 0.106	0.176 \pm 0.021	1.235 \pm 0.100
Glucose + amino acids	13.548 \pm 1.466	15.522 \pm 0.871	8.680 \pm 0.440
pDNA volumetric yield (mg/L)			
Glucose	1.760 \pm 0.368	2.180 \pm 1.457	2.180 \pm 0.622
Glycerol	10.770 \pm 0.325	11.435 \pm 2.044	9.900 \pm 0.806
Glucose + amino acids	3.335 \pm 1.039	2.310 \pm 0.014	2.060 \pm 0.226
pDNA specific yield (mg/g DCW)			
Glucose	1.354 \pm 0.135	1.839 \pm 0.417	1.381 \pm 0.133
Glycerol	5.244 \pm 0.069	8.796 \pm 0.475	5.417 \pm 0.009
Glucose + amino acids	11.365 \pm 0.623	3.447 \pm 0.355	3.562 \pm 0.094
SC fraction at 24h (%)			
Glucose	67.34 \pm 13.93	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00
Glycerol	59.16 \pm 14.96	75.77 \pm 8.31	91.16 \pm 0.07
Glucose + amino acids	76.35 \pm 2.02	82.02 \pm 1.54	86.50 \pm 2.54

siderable precipitation, while the glycerol medium showed minor precipitation, and the Wang medium had none. Since the glycerol medium has the same composition as the glucose medium, except for the carbon source, it is hypothesized that the higher viscosity of glycerol could have partially prevented salt precipitation. Consequently, the poor performance observed in the glucose medium was possibly exacerbated by this precipitation, further deviating from expected behavior, while the glycerol and Wang media behaved more closely to theoretical expectations.

Indeed, the glucose-based medium resulted in the least expected outcomes: it should have exhibited higher growth rates, more biomass, less acetate accumulation, and higher volumetric and specific pDNA yields, particularly for GALG20, since the *pgi* knockout is expected to enhance these parameters when glucose is used. The absence of these results for all strains may be attributed to precipitation, which reduced nutrient availability and induced stress. In the case of GALG20, this may have redirected carbon flux toward alternative pathways, instead of the PP pathway, as previously discussed. This stress may also have affected pDNA structural stability, explaining the absence of the SC isoform after 24h. The

increased presence of high-molecular-weight bands, likely multimers, may indicate impaired multimer-resolution systems, which have been reported to be inhibited when high-osmolarity media are used. In this work, such bands were observed only for the glucose- and glycerol-based Listner media and not in the Wang medium. Since osmolarity increases with salt concentration and the Listner medium contains higher levels of salts than Wang medium, it is plausible that the high osmolarity of Listner medium contributed not only to salt precipitation but also to inhibition of multimer resolution [65].

As expected, glycerol led to slower metabolism and lower specific growth rates, maintaining the cells in the exponential phase for longer. This resulted in the highest biomass (2-fold greater than glucose) and the lowest acetate accumulation from the tested media, for all strains. The higher biomass contributed to a 5-fold increase in volumetric pDNA yield compared to glucose, also for all strains. Glycerol metabolism also increases NADH availability, influencing cellular physiology and plasmid maintenance, favoring carbon flux toward product formation, as reflected in the 5-fold increase in specific yield [116]. The higher SC fraction obtained can be explained by cultures remaining in the exponential phase, avoiding the stationary phase where instability increases. Also, given that less precipitation occurred, nutrient limitation and cell stress were reduced, contributing to improved plasmid stability.

As for the Wang medium, growth and biomass were lower, as expected, since amino acid limitation slows protein synthesis and growth. This slower growth provides a larger window for plasmid replication before cell division, reducing stress and improving plasmid quality. Consequently, volumetric yield decreases and specific yield increases, as more carbon is redirected from biomass formation to plasmid synthesis. This effect is particularly noticeable in DH5 α , which, due to its *relA1* mutation, does not activate the stringent response under nutrient limitation. The higher SC fraction supports this, indicating reduced stress and better energetic balance, likely linked to shifts in intracellular ATP/ADP ratios.

Since the high-molecular-weight band was observed in both glucose and glycerol-based Listner media, its identity as potential multimers and confirmation that it corresponded to the intended plasmid, pVAX1-GFP, were further investigated. For this purpose, two restriction enzyme digestions were performed: one using EcoRI, which cuts pVAX1-GFP once at the 5'-GAATTC-3' site, and another using BamHI, which cuts twice at 5'-GGATCC-3'. Digestion with EcoRI is expected to result in a linear fragment of 3697 bp, and BamHI digestion should result in two fragments of approximately 730 bp and 2967 bp (Fig. A.1). The expected bands were indeed detected in all samples (Fig. A.11), although with different intensities and incomplete digestion of the high-molecular-weight band. The digestion suggests that the plasmid corresponds to pVAX1-GFP, possibly in multimeric forms. The incomplete digestion could result from steric hindrance caused by large multimers, which could limit the accessibility of restriction enzymes [117]. Alternatively, the faint residual band after digestion could represent gDNA contamination, as reported by O'Kennedy *et al.* (2003), who observed that prolonged stationary phase cultivation increased gDNA contamination [89]. However, given that most of the initial band was digested, the

evidence supports that this should indeed correspond to multimers.

Regarding data quality for parameter estimation in future model development, the different strains in glucose-based Listner medium (Fig. A.12) showed acceptable consistency except for a few outliers. However, pDNA values showed high variability and irregular trends, likely due to limitations of the purification kit, which proved unreliable for low plasmid concentrations, as confirmed by poor $A_{260/280}$ and $A_{260/230}$ ratios. A similar trend was seen for the glycerol-based Listner medium (Fig. A.13), although samples with higher pDNA concentrations, as the 24h time point, exhibited optimal purity ratios, highlighting method inaccuracy at low concentrations. For the Wang-based medium (Fig. A.14), inconsistencies were also observed in both pDNA and HPLC data, possibly due to overlapping of unidentified peaks near the retention time of glucose and acetate, since noisier chromatographic profiles were obtained in comparison with the other media.

A better approach for sampling should be adopted, with similar inoculum age and uninterrupted growth between the two experimental sets to obtain fully complementary datasets. More robust purification and quantification techniques should be explored and employed, such as alkaline lysis followed by quantification determined by Hydrophobic Interaction Chromatography (HIC) [94].

5. Conclusions and Future Work

5.1 Final Conclusions

Over recent years, the global demand for pDNA has risen significantly, driven by its key role in gene and cell therapies, vaccines and immunotherapies. As these therapies progress through clinical trials and regulatory approvals, the need for scalable, high-yield and cost-effective manufacturing processes has become extremely urgent. However, challenges in reproducibility and compliance with GMP standards make scaling up a major bottleneck, often delaying regulatory approval. To address these limitations, regulatory authorities emphasize the need for comprehensive process understanding and control, achievable through modeling approaches and QbD frameworks. In this context, digitalization, particularly through the development of digital twins, has emerged as a transformative strategy, enabling real-time monitoring, process control, and data-driven optimization. Yet, the successful creation of accurate and predictive digital twins fundamentally relies on the availability of high-quality and robust experimental data that reliably capture process dynamics.

In this context, the present research aimed to generate reliable experimental data as a foundation for developing a digital twin for pDNA production, while evaluating the influence of strain engineering and medium composition on pDNA production. For this purpose, three *E. coli* strains were employed: DH5 α (control), MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (parental), and GALG20 (engineered). The GALG20 strain, developed by Gonçalves *et al.* (2013), was reported to produce 25-fold more pDNA than its parental strain due to a *pgi* knockout that redirects carbon flux to the PP pathway, enhancing precursor synthesis and reducing overflow metabolism [18]. In this work, the parental strain was successfully constructed through a *recA* knockout using the λ Red recombination system, described by Datsenko and Wanner (2000), which was confirmed by sequencing after optimization of arabinose concentration, recovery time and temperature [50]. Then, comparative growth experiments were conducted with both non-transformed and pDNA-harboring strains (pVAX1-GFP), using chemically defined media by Listner *et al.* (2006) and Wang *et al.* (2001), differing in carbon source and amino acid composition to assess their influence on cell growth and pDNA production [2, 78]. These media were selected for their reproducibility and suitability for fermentation modeling. Substrate consumption and metabolite formation were analyzed by HPLC, and pDNA yield, quality, and isoform distribution were evaluated.

Overall, the results demonstrated that medium composition had the strongest influence on performance. The glycerol-based medium yielded 2-fold higher biomass and up to a 5-fold increase in pDNA specific yield, compared to glucose, while minimizing acetate accumulation and preserving SC pDNA fraction. The highest volumetric yield was obtained for MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* in the glycerol-based medium (11.44 mg/L). In contrast, the glucose-based medium underperformed most notably, with reduced growth, elevated acetate accumulation, and complete loss of the SC fraction after 24 h, likely due

to precipitation and limited nutrient availability, inducing cellular stress. The Wang medium, although supporting slower growth, produced the highest pDNA quality, with SC fractions exceeding 76% for all strains, confirming the positive effect of amino acid limitation on plasmid stability. The highest specific yield observed was 11.37 mg/g_{DCW} in DH5 α , under Wang medium, due to its genetic background resulting in a relaxed stringent response. Multimeric pDNA forms were detected in both glucose- and glycerol-based Listner media, but not in the Wang medium. This supports the hypothesis that medium osmolarity and stress conditions can impair multimer resolution mechanisms, leading to reduced pDNA stability and product quality. When comparing the metabolic burden imposed by pDNA production in these cultivation conditions, the growth rate both increased or decreased depending on the specific case, with some statistically significant differences. However, in general, pDNA production did not substantially impact the growth rate. These findings demonstrate the complex interplay between media composition, carbon source, and metabolic regulation in determining pDNA yield and quality.

All strains exhibited lower performance than reported in the literature, likely due to the use of chemically defined media instead of richer complex media, as in the case of Listner media, or due to differences in cultivation mode, for the Wang medium. Specifically, when comparing strains, GALG20 did not outperform in any tested medium, resulting in a volumetric yield up to 64-fold lower than reported (2.180 mg/L vs 140.8 mg/L). This suggests that the anticipated metabolic advantage conferred by the *pgi* knockout was not evident under the tested defined media conditions, likely due to poor nutrient availability and resulting metabolic stress. Such conditions may have redirected carbon flux toward alternative pathways, such as the ED pathway, reducing precursor availability for pDNA synthesis and contributing to overflow metabolism. As defined media are essential for digital twin development, further medium optimisation or supplementation may be required, or alternatively, GALG20 may not be the most suitable strain for accurate modelling in this context.

Together, these results highlight that medium composition exerted a stronger influence than genetic background under the tested conditions, underscoring the need for experimental data for different strains using different media rather than relying on literature-based assumptions. This further highlights the importance of a holistic optimization approach, balancing strain engineering, medium formulation, and metabolic control to maximize productivity.

Beyond the biological insights, this work generated an integrated dataset combining growth kinetics, metabolite profiles, pDNA yields and isoform ratios across different strains and media, which can serve as the input for mechanistic modelling and predictive process understanding. Despite some variability in pDNA quantification and some inconsistencies between datasets, this experimental framework established a valuable foundation for future kinetic model calibration and parameter estimation. Refining media composition, improving sampling strategies, and enhancing purification and quantification accuracy are expected to further improve predictive capacity.

These findings form a pioneering step toward the development of the first predictive digital twin of pDNA production in batch mode. To date, digital twins have only been implemented for mRNA-based SARS-COVID-19 vaccine manufacturing, and a distinct one is under development for fully digitalized continuous pDNA production lines [75, 118]. By integrating the experimental foundation obtained with metabolic and kinetic modeling, including strain-specific flux information, it will be possible to simulate and optimize production across strains, media, and cultivation modes. Such approaches will ultimately support data-driven optimization, process understanding, regulatory validation, and the advancement of smart biomanufacturing strategies for pDNA.

5.2 Limitations and Future Work

Although this work generated some valuable insights about strain and medium effects on pDNA production, several limitations have been identified and require future work.

First, the glucose Listner-based medium underperformed considerably, likely because nutrient precipitation reduced availability and induced cellular stress. To address this, the precipitate should be identified, e.g. by lyophilization followed by X-ray diffraction, and concentrations of implicated components, probably phosphate and thiamine, should be adjusted. A promising next step is to test the Wang medium with glycerol instead of glucose, to combine the advantages of amino acid limitation with the higher pDNA yields from glycerol.

Another significant issue was the presence of high-molecular-weight bands in purified pDNA gels, which likely represent multimers, but may also reflect a small amount of gDNA. To resolve this, methods such as quantitative real-time PCR, long-read sequencing or capillary electrophoresis should be employed [40]. Control experiments in a rich medium, e.g. LB medium, or purifying directly from the inoculum, could help determine whether the phenomenon is strain- or medium-dependent and at what point it is produced.

Several observations suggest that stress responses are activated under the tested conditions. To clarify this, methods to measure the physiological burden on the strains should be employed, including flow cytometry (assessing membrane polarization), microscopy (for signs of filamentation), fluorescence spectroscopy (monitoring intracellular NADH/FAD levels as indicators of redox state), and transcriptomic profiling (for changes in *rpoS* and other stress-response genes) [15, 78].

Furthermore, other results suggest an unexpected flux redirection for GALG20 in the tested conditions. To fully elucidate this, advanced methods such as ¹³C-metabolic flux analysis or flux balance analysis are recommended. A significant issue identified was acetate accumulation. Consequently, further strain engineering, such as activating the glyoxylate shunt pathway by knocking out *fruR*, could enhance performance.

The consistency and accuracy of pDNA quantification was also limited, primarily due to low pDNA

concentrations, contributing to high variability and reduced purity ratios. Consequently, a more robust purification protocol should be adopted, such as alkaline lysis with concentration by isopropanol and protein precipitation by ammonium sulfate, followed by an optimized HIC method, as detailed by Diogo *et al.* (2003), which is capable of handling contaminated samples with low content of pDNA [119].

Concerning cultivation strategy, several parameters could be further explored. Alternative chemically defined media, such as M9 medium, or mixtures of carbon sources, such as glucose and glycerol, to conjugate high plasmid yields associated with glycerol with rapid growth supported by glucose, could be tested [12, 21]. Process variables, including agitation rate (e.g. increasing to 400 rpm to improve oxygen transfer) and temperature shifts (e.g. growing at 30°C then shifting to 42°C for plasmid amplification) could also be explored and optimized [12, 62, 95]. Future work should also involve testing additional engineered strains under varying initial conditions, while integrating metabolic and kinetic modelling approaches to better capture strain-specific behaviours and process dynamics.

Finally, from a modeling perspective, improving data quality and consistency is crucial. The sampling strategy should be optimized, e.g. with the second set starting at ~6h rather than 10h, to synchronize with the actual growth time of the first set. In addition, using inocula of the same age and reducing the frequency of pH sampling should further enhance the comparability and integrity of the datasets.

Regarding the future kinetic model, additional parameters must be included to enable predictions from shake-flask data to bioreactor performance. Varying both strain and medium combinations in a DoE approach would help quantify the strain-medium interaction effects. Also, since oxygen limitation is a key difference in scale-up, the model should introduce a variable representing dissolved oxygen concentration, reflecting the different volumetric oxygen-transfer coefficient ($k_L a$) and working volume. Similarly, since the carbon to nitrogen (C:N) ratio has been shown to influence pDNA production, it is essential to also model nitrogen concentration, e.g. following stoichiometric approaches such as those employed by Wang *et al.* (2001) [2, 12]. Ultimately, to mitigate the challenge posed by limited experimental data, synthetic data generation approaches should be applied to expand the dataset for refined parameter estimation. Experimentally, to obtain richer datasets in bioreactors, digital methodologies should be employed, such as *in situ* monitoring with near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy combined with Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression, to reduce sampling efforts and minimize contamination risk while enabling continuous process monitoring [94].

Altogether, these efforts should establish a robust and reliable foundation for a predictive digital twin of pDNA production.

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Appendix

Sequence of pVAX1-GFP plasmid (3697 bp):

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1 GACTCTTCGC GATGTACGGG CCAGATATAC GCGTTGACAT TGATTATTGA CTAGTTATTA
61 ATAGTAATCA ATTACGGGGT CATTAGTTCA TAGCCCATAT ATGGAGTTCC GCGTTACATA
121 ACTTACGGTA AATGGCCCCG CTGGCTGACC GCCCAACGAC CCCC GCCCAT TGACGTCAAT
181 AATGACGTAT GTTCCCATAG TAACGCCAAT AGGGACTTTC CATTGACGTC AATGGGTGGA
241 CTATTACGG TAAACTGCC ACTTGGCAGT ACATCAAGTG TATCATATGC CAAGTACGCC
301 CCCTATTGAC GTCAATGACG GTAAATGGCC CGCCTGGCAT TATGCCAGT ACATGACCTT
361 ATGGGACTTT CCTACTTGGC AGTACATCTA CGTATTAGTC ATCGCTATTA CCATGGTGAT
421 GCGGTTTTGG CAGTACATCA ATGGGCGTGG ATAGCGGTTT GACTCACGGG GATTTCCAAG
481 TCTCCACCCC ATTGACGTCA ATGGGAGTTT GTTTTGGCAC CAAAATCAAC GGGACTTTCC
541 AAAATGTCGT AACAACTCCG CCCATTGAC GCAAATGGGC GGTAGGCGTG TACGGTGGGA
601 GGTCTATATA AGCAGAGCTC TCTGGCTAAC TAGAGAACC ACTGCTTACT GGCTTATCGA
661 AATTAATACG ACTCACTATA GGGAGACCCA AGCTGGTAG CGTTTAACT TAAGCTTGGT
721 ACCGAGCTCG GATCCACTAG TCCAGTGTGG TGGAATTCGC ATATGGTGAG CAAGGGCGAG
781 GAGCTGTTC CCGGGGTGGT GCCCATCCTG GTCGAGCTGG ACGGCGACGT AACGGCCAC
841 AAGTTCAGCG TGTCCGGCGA GGGCGAGGGC GATGCCACCT ACGGCAAGCT GACCCTGAAG
901 TTCATCTGCA CCACCGGCAA GCTGCCCGTG CCCTGGCCCA CCCTCGTGAC CACCCTGACC
961 TACGGCGTGC AGTGCTTCA CCGTACCCC GACCACATGA AGCAGCACGA CTTCTTCAAG
1021 TCCGCCATGC CCGAAGGCTA CGTCCAGGAG CGCACCATCT TCTTCAAGGA CGACGGCAAC
1081 TACAAGACCC GCGCCGAGGT GAAGTTCGAG GGCGACACCC TGGTGAACCG CATCGAGCTG
1141 AAGGGCATCG ACTTCAAGGA GGACGGCAAC ATCCTGGGGC ACAAGCTGGA GTACAACACT
1201 AACAGCCACA ACGTCTATAT CATGGCCGAC AAGCAGAAGA ACGGCATCAA GGTGAACTTC
1261 AAGATCCGCC ACAACATCGA GGACGGCAGC GTGCAGCTCG CCGACCACTA CCAGCAGAAC
1321 ACCCCATCGC GCGACGGCCC CGTGCTGCTG CCGACAACC ACTACCTGAG CACCAGTCC
1381 GCCCTGAGCA AAGACCCCAA CGAGAAGCGC GATCACATGG TCCTGTGTTG GATTCGTGAC
1441 GCCGCCGGGA TCACCTCTCG CATGGACGAG CTGTACAAGT AATGGATCCT CTAGAGGGCC
1501 CGTTTAAACC CGCTGATCAG CCTCGACTGT GCCTTCTAGT TGCCAGCCAT CTGTTGTTTG
1561 CCCCTCCCC GTGCCTTCTT TGACCCTGGA AGGTGCCACT CCCACTGTCC TTTCTAATA
1621 AAATGAGGAA ATTGCATCGC ATTGTCTGAG TAGGTGTCAT TCTATTCTGG GGGGTGGGGT
1681 GGGGCAGGAC AGCAAGGGGG AGGATTGGGA AGACAATAGC AGGCATGCTG GGGATGCGGT
1741 GGGCTCTATG GCTTCTACTG GGCGGTTTTA TGGACAGCAA GCGAACCGBA ATTGCCAGCT
1801 GGGGCGCCCT CTGGTAAGGT TGGGAAGCCC TGCAAAGTAA ACTGGATGGC TTTCTCGCCG
1861 CCAAGGATCT GATGGCGCAG GGGATCAAGC TCTGATCAAG AGACAGGATG AGGATCGTTT
1921 CGCATGATTG AACAAAGTGG ATTGCACGCA GGTTCTCCGG CCGCTTGGGT GGAGAGGCTA
1981 TTCGGCTATG ACTGGGCACA ACAGACAATC GGCTGCTCTG ATGCCGCCGT GTTCCGGCTG
2041 TCAGCGCAGG GCGCCCGGT TCTTTTTGTC AAGACCGACC TGTCCGGTGC CCTGAATGAA
2101 CTGCAAGACG AGGCAGCGCG GCTATCGTGG CTGGCCACGA CCGGCGTTCC TTGCGCAGCT
2161 GTGCTCGACG TTGTCACTGA AGCGGGAAGG GACTGGCTGC TATTGGGCGA AGTGCCGGGG
2221 CAGGATCTCC TGTCATCTCA CTTTCTCCT GCCGAGAAAG TATCCATCAT GGCTGATGCA
2281 ATGCGGCGGC TGCATACGCT TGATCCGGCT ACCTGCCCAT TCGACCACCA AGCGAAACAT
2341 CGCATCGAGC GAGCACGTAC TCGGATGGAA GCCGGTCTTG TCGATCAGGA TGATCTGGAC
2401 GAAGAGCATC AGGGGCTCGC GCCAGCCGAA CTGTTCCGCC GGCTCAAGGC GAGCATGCC
2461 GACGGCGAGG ATCTCGTCTG GACCCATGGC GATGCTGCTG TGCCGAATAT CATGGTGGAA
2521 AATGGCCGCT TTTCTGGATT CATCGACTGT GGCCGGCTGG GTGTGGCGGA CCGTATCAG
2581 GACATAGCGT TGGTACCCG TGATATTGCT GAAGAGCTTG GCGGCGAATG GGCTGACCGC
2641 TTCCTCGTGC TTTACGGTAT CGCCGCTCCC GATTGCGAGC GCATGCTT CTATGCTT
2701 CTTGACGAGT TCTTCTGAAT TATTAACGCT TACAATTTCC TGATGCGGTA TTTTCTCCTT
2761 ACGCATCTGT GCGGTATTTT ACACCGCATA CAGGTGGCAC TTTTCCGGGA AATGTGCGCG
2821 GAACCCCTAT TTGTTTATTT TTCTAAATAC ATTCAAATAT GTATCCGCTC ATGAGACAAT
2881 AACCCGTGATA AATGCTTCAA TAATAGCACG TGCTAAAATC TCATTTTTAA TTTAAAAGGA
2941 TCTAGGTGAA GATCCTTTTT GATAATCTCA TGACCAAATC CCCTTAACGT GAGTTTTCTG
3001 TCCACTGAGC GTCAGACCCC GTAGAAAAGA TCAAAGGATC TTCTTGAGAT CCTTTTTTTC
3061 TGCGCGTAAT CTGCTGCTTG CAAACAAAAA AACACCGCT ACCAGCGGTG GTTTGTTTGC
3121 CGGATCAAGA GCTACCAACT CTTTTTCCGA AGGTAAGTGG CTTCAGCAGA GCGCAGATAC
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3181 CAAATACTGT CCTTCTAGTG TAGCCGTAGT TAGGCCACCA CTTCAAGAAC TCTGTAGCAC
 3241 CGCCTACATA CCTCGCTCTG CTAATCCTGT TACCAGTGGC TGCTGCCAGT GGCGATAAGT
 3301 CGTGTCTTAC CGGGTTGGAC TCAAGACGAT AGTTACCGGA TAAGGCGCAG CGGTCGGGCT
 3361 GAACGGGGGG TTCGTGCACA CAGCCCAGCT TGGAGCGAAC GACCTACACC GAACTGAGAT
 3421 ACCTACAGCG TGAGCTATGA GAAAGCGCCA CGCTTCCCGA AGGGAGAAAAG GCGGACAGGT
 3481 ATCCGGTAAG CGGCAGGGTC GGAACAGGAG AGCGCACGAG GGAGCTTCCA GGGGGAAACG
 3541 CCTGGTATCT TTATAGTCTC GTCGGGTTTC GCCACCTCTG ACTTGAGCGT CGATTTTTGT
 3601 GATGCTGCTC AGGGGGGCGG AGCCTATGGA AAAACGCCAG CAACGCGGCC TTTTACGGT
 3661 TCCTGGGCTT TTGCTGGCCT TTTGCTCACA TGTTCTT

Figure A.1: Plasmid pVAX1-GFP, with restriction recognition sites highlighted for EcoRI (light blue) and BamHI (dark blue). Constructed with SnapGene.

Figure A.2: Plasmids used for the gene knockout, designed according to the Datsenko and Wanner protocol for the λ Red recombination system. A: pKD46[79]; B: pCP20[80]; C: pKD13[81].

Figure A.3: Composition of the NZYDNA Ladder III.

Figure A.4: Standard calibration curves and respective equations for acetate (A), glucose (B) and glycerol (C). The retention time for acetate was 19.8 min, 19.18 min for glycerol and 13.75 min for glucose.

Figure A.5: Agarose gel electrophoresis of purified pDNA of GALG20 and GALG20+pDNA in Listner-based medium at different initial glucose concentrations at the 24h time point. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 - GALG20 at 5 g/L; 3 - GALG20 at 10 g/L; 4 - GALG20 at 20 g/L.

Figure A.6: Agarose gel electrophoresis of purified pDNA of DH5 α , MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA and GALG20 in Listner glucose-based medium, for 12h (yellow), 15h (green), 18h (blue) and 24h (pink). SC - supercoiled. Lanes for each hour: L - NZYDNA Ladder III; 1 - DH5 α (1); 2 - DH5 α (2); 3 - MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (1); 4 - MG1655 Δ endA Δ recA (2); 5 - GALG20(1); 6 - GALG20(2).

Figure A.7: Agarose gel electrophoresis of purified pDNA of DH5 α and DH5 α +pDNA in Listner-based medium at different initial glycerol concentrations at the 24h time point. Lanes: 1 - NZYDNA Ladder III; 2 - DH5 α at 5 g/L; 3 - DH5 α at 10 g/L; 4 - DH5 α at 20 g/L.

Figure A.8: Agarose gel electrophoresis of purified pDNA of DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* and GALG20 in Listner glycerol-based medium for 12h (yellow), 15h (green), 18h (blue) and 24h (pink). SC - supercoiled. Lanes for each hour: L - NZYDNA Ladder III; 1 - DH5 α (1); 2 - DH5 α (2); 3 - MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (1); 4 - MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (2); 5 - GALG20(1); 6 - GALG20(2).

Figure A.9: Stoichiometric model for pDNA production, employed by Wang. *et al* (2001). [2].

Figure A.10: Agarose gel electrophoresis of purified pDNA of DH5 α , MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* and GALG20 in Wang glucose-based medium for 12h (yellow), 15h (green), 18h (blue) and 24h (pink). SC - supercoiled. Lanes for each hour: L - NZYDNA Ladder III; 1 - DH5 α (1); 2 - DH5 α (2); 3 - MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (1); 4 - MG1655 Δ *endA* Δ *recA* (2); 5 - GALG20(1); 6 - GALG20(2).

Figure A.11: Agarose gel electrophoresis of purified pDNA displaying apparent multimers, after digestion with EcoRI (left) and BamHI (right). Lanes for each gel: L - NZYDNA Ladder III; 1 - DH5 α 24h in glycerol Listner-based medium; 2 - GALG20 18h in 10 g/L of glucose in Listner-based medium; 3 - GALG20 12h in glucose Listner-based medium; 4 - GALG20 15h in glucose Listner-based medium.

Figure A.12: Biomass formation (green), glucose consumption (blue), acetate production (yellow) and pDNA production (red) of DH5 α (top), MG1655 $\Delta endA \Delta recA$ (middle) and GALG20 (bottom) in Listner glucose-based medium for 24h. The mean results (n=2) of two replicates for each strain are presented, along with standard deviation error bars. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

Figure A.13: Biomass formation (green), glucose consumption (blue), acetate production (yellow) and pDNA production (red) of DH5 α (top), MG1655 $\Delta endA \Delta recA$ (middle) and GALG20 (bottom) in Listner glycerol-based medium for 24h. The mean results (n=2) of two replicates for each strain are presented, along with standard deviation error bars. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.

Figure A.14: Biomass formation (green), glucose consumption (blue), acetate production (yellow) and pDNA production (red) of DH5 α (top), MG1655 $\Delta endA \Delta recA$ (middle) and GALG20 (bottom) in Wang glucose-based medium for 24h. The mean results (n=2) of two replicates for each strain are presented, along with standard deviation error bars. Strains were grown in shake flasks at 37°C and 250 rpm.